

Acoustic monitoring of wind turbine noise emission with spatial filtering arrays for continuous wind park investigations

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Declaration

No portion of this work referred to in this thesis has been submitted in support of an application for another degree or qualification from this or any other university or other institution of learning.

Abstract

The emitted noise sound is part of the concerns about wind parks but also contains information about the wind turbine operation and potential failures. Continuous acoustic monitoring in wind parks has the potential to oversee noise levels and process sound signals related to failures at a wind turbine, e.g., at the blades' surfaces or gearbox faults. For investigations into wind turbine sounds, a spatial assignment of noise sources is needed to separate sounds from turbine parts from background noise. In this research, the aim is to develop systems and techniques for applications in noise emission monitoring and spatial sound assignment at wind turbines in wind parks. To fulfil this aim, a significant part of this research project was focused on the development of a suitable microphone array monitoring hardware that is robust enough to withstand outdoors continuous environmental conditions for wind park acoustic measurement deployment. Microphone arrays are due to their arrangement of multiple microphones capable of spatially separating sound sources. The array development includes a suitable microphone unit, an acoustically transparent protective membrane for the microphones, the design of an outdoor array containing 64 microphones and the firmware for the processors in the system. A new development was necessary because there are neither suitable measuring instruments nor designs for robust acoustic arrays available in literature or on the market. The appropriate wind park application of the developed hardware was made to record wind turbine noise with the boundary conditions of noise recording standards. The results from the applied array hardware were compared to the current standards for wind turbine noise measurements, which do not cover the continuous observation at wind turbines. The data collection campaign was performed during two seasons of the year in the wind park. In 9 weeks of wind park operation, a total of 76 hours of acoustic, environmental and wind turbine operation data was collected in different conditions. This data has been analysed for noise emission monitoring and have been spatially filtered for acoustic turbine part observation. This work successfully showed that an acoustic array can be deployed long-term in a fixed location to continuously monitor noise emissions in

a wind park for the first time and proved that the results of this approach are comparable with the current standard. Secondly, it has successfully demonstrated its performance in combating noise emissions by being used in a wind farm for 9 weeks and under various environmental conditions and delivering reliable noise level data. Thirdly, it has shown that automated spatial filtering can be used to localise noise signals to specific parts of the wind turbine which can be further analysed for fault detection. The research showed that with an advanced robust acoustic array monitoring system the high demand for noise investigations at wind turbines can be served.

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List of Publications

- 1 T. Wenzel, R. Rettig, 2021, Design of MEMS microphone protective membranes for continuous outdoor applications, peer reviewed research paper, Applied Acoustics [1]
- 2 T. Wenzel, D. Rokita, F. Ueberle, R. Rettig, 2017, ACOUSTIC INTERNET-OF-THINGS: LOW-COST, DISTRIBUTED, SYNCHRONOUS MEASUREMENT SYSTEMS FOR AUTOMATED SOUND SOURCE LOCALIZATION IN WIND TURBINES, talk, ICSV24; London [2]
- 3 T. Wenzel, 2016, Development of a synchronous multichannel measurement system for air-borne and solid-borne sound, Master thesis [3]
- 4 T. Wenzel, Noise, and a way to develop countermeasures, 2021, Annual Research Student Conference, Presentation, 2021, Paisley, Scotland (Price winning presentation) [4]
- 5 T. Wenzel, Wind turbines sound emission: Robust, 24/7, acoustical monitoring system with spatial filtering, 2020, Annual Research Student Conference, Talk, 2020, Paisley, Scotland [5]

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List of Abbreviation

Abbreviation	Meaning
ADC	Analogue digital converter
BLCK	Bit clock
CLEAN SC	Clean beamforming based on Source Coherence
dBASPL	A-weighted decibel sound pressure level
DOA	Direction of arrival
FPGA	Field programmable gate array
FEM	Finite element methods
IC	Integrated circuit
LRCLK	Left right clock
LIDAR	Light detection and ranging
MEMS	Microelectromechanical system
MSM	Multi sensor microphone
NNW	North-north-west
PC	Personal computer
PCB	Printed circuit board

PSF	Point spread function
RH	Relative humidity
SDATA	Serial data
SUT	System under test
TDM	Time division multiplexing
TDOA	Time direction of arrival
USB	Universal serial bus
WT	Wind turbine

Chapter 1 Introductions

Nowadays, a significant part of electrical power is generated by wind turbines and the transmission to renewable plays a significant part in CO₂-reduction [6], [7]. The demand for onshore wind energy generates conflicts in land use and challenges in controlling noise emissions from wind parks. Emerging onshore wind parks with demand for maximum power output and largest runtimes are working against efforts to reduce noise for local residents. To balance conflicting needs, a monitoring system can supply quantitative information on noise emissions and valuable operational information about the wind turbine conditions. Both are required to operate a wind park in noise sensitive environments.

In wind parks, an effective use of the available wind power leads to an increase in run-time demand and increased dimensions of modern wind turbines. Both developments in wind energy have led to increased noise pollution in the vicinity of a wind park. On the other hand, wind turbine noise contains information about the operating states of the turbine and detailed information of wind turbine parts conditions, e.g. vibrational frequencies in the nacelle or defects on blade surfaces [8] that emit whistling noises. Measuring sound emissions in a wind farm supplies valuable information about turbine conditions to the operator. Information about the position and frequency range of turbine signals are processed by my approach. The method of continuously recording noise emissions in a wind park developed in this work supplies the information input for the two presented tasks. The solution presented in this thesis requires the development of an acoustic monitoring system.

Due to the increasing number of onshore wind turbines and limited existing land area, noise increases in inhabited settlements because of shrinking distances to the wind parks. Noise is even more raised by the growing height of modern wind turbines and their swept area. The average installed wind turbine power increased from 1 MW in the year 2001 to 2.6 MW in the year 2018 and is forecasted to increase to 5.8 MW in 2025 [9]. In the same period the average rotor diameter grew from 50 m to 110.4 m and is expected to reach 170 m in the year 2025. These are forecasted to increase to 5.8 MW and 170 m in 2025 [9, p. 40]. These significant changes affect the overall turbine height and the sound travel distances. To minimise the noise with the size development in the upcoming years, an effective way of noise control measures is needed. These measures could be deduced from the data recorded by an acoustic monitoring system that directly records noise in the wind park. The problem with the standard one-channel recordings [10] is the missing information of the noise source position. For example, an exact source position of a surface defect on a blade increased the usability of my approach for maintenance purposes. Other than a single-channel recording device, an acoustic array with multiple recording channels is developed in this research and it generates a spatial separation feature for detailed investigations on noise sources.

With the focus on onshore wind park operation, the overall goal of efforts is to maximise the energy output of the turbine. This leads to an overall reduced CO₂ footprint since more electrical power is sourced from the wind. To achieve high power outputs, the turbine must operate in optimal conditions with minimum downtime. A low downtime can be achieved by implementing effective maintenance of the wind turbines. That can be difficult since turbines are located at remote locations. But it can be facilitated with the use of a system that continuously monitors the sound of the turbine and records noise events of turbine parts at the moment when they occur. This data could be fed into another system to detect potential events of failures. The data analysis towards condition monitoring and preventive maintenance is part of future research and is not covered in this work. An acoustic array placed a in short distance to the turbine can separate noise sources at the turbine and can suppress background noise for better analytical results. Assigning noise levels to multiple turbines in a wind park with an acoustic array enables interventions into

every turbine's controller for location-dependent noise control. The pitch control at the turbine reduces the rotational speed and with this the noise level and is an approach of controlling the wind park emissions. This approach can be part of future research that uses the data recorded in this work. With this approach, the array of data could be used for noise reduction for crucial objects in the surroundings.

The operation of wind turbines is always in the area of tension between the operator and the affected residents. The residents require a quiet environment, and the operator wants to set up as many turbines in an area as possible and wants them to run in their maximum energy output conditions as long as possible. The issue that comes with the maximum power output is it generates continuously the highest noise levels. This leads to the need for acoustic monitoring in wind parks. These two aspects of noise monitoring in wind parks are shown in Figure 1 with the two chains of reasoning. Therefore, the illustration provides the connection between the occurring noise issue in wind park with increasing turbine sizes and the aspect of the array delivering data for future analysis of noise data. It is crucial that the measured data are recorded with an acoustic array, with that the analysis algorithms can separate noise sources between the turbine and the background and can locate potential failing turbine parts. The challenge of array applications in the wind park scenario is to record sounds in the occurring noise frequency range and use a robust array that can withstand the environmental influences. The second aspect of the ruggedized array is the biggest challenge because every method of protection in the array will affect the acoustic behaviour and performance of the recording microphones.

In wind parks multiple noise sources are present. The emitting noise sources other than the wind turbine emission are unrelated to the wind turbines and are interpreted as background or surrounding noise levels. Separating those noise sources and their levels from the additional level emitted by the turbine can only be made with an accurate spatial allocation of sources. With this capability, a detailed wind turbine noise image with their overall emissions and turbine part noise levels is processed.

Figure 1: Diagram of an acoustic monitoring system application at a wind park; displaying the left argumentative chain towards maximum power output and the right argumentative chain towards an increased noise load in the wind park surroundings, the blue box of the acoustic monitoring system is part of this research project

The literature is providing a wide range of microphone array applications, many apply acoustic arrays in wind parks for noise investigations [11]–[15]. Acoustic array developments in recent years show a movement toward digital Microelectromechanical systems (MEMS) microphones with attached processing units [16]–[18]. Mostly the developed units are designed as handheld devices for single measurements usage. Available array hardware is designed for indoor laboratory measurements and is limited to periods of clear weather outdoors for wind park measurements. Enabling continuous measurements in wind parks would cover more operational states of wind turbines and enhance the understanding of noise emissions in these times. Presenting a MEMS-based system with attached processing and designing a structure for outdoor

usage in this work combines the advantages of recent microelectronics development and robust acoustic devices for the first time.

This research is driven by one main question which is used to develop multiple sub-questions. Each sub-question is needed for detailed investigation and combined they are used to answer the main question of the research.

How can an array monitoring system be applied continuously in a wind park for noise monitoring and noise source localization on wind turbines?

Two aspects of the wind park application are addressed by the formulation, the first is the definition or development of an acoustic monitoring system that can supply the needed information for the task. The second describes the two applications of the system and addresses the two challenges of wind turbine operation.

The overall goal of this research project is to develop an acoustic monitoring system, which uses a microphone array for the separation of sound sources at wind turbines and processes condition information about the wind turbine based on the spatially filtered signals. The main challenge is the development of measures to make the array robust for the wind park application and to get good acoustic performance results with one design. The general goal can be further divided into subtasks that this project needs to carry out:

- Identification of requirements for noise monitoring of wind turbines
- Development of a microphone array
- Measuring sound emissions of wind turbines in a wind park
- Noise monitoring development using a microphone array
- Implementation of spatial sound separation at wind turbines

Subtasks are divided into further subtasks, which are addressed in more detail in the following chapters of this thesis.

Chapter 2 covers the technical background of wind turbine emissions, acoustic monitoring systems, and recent noise investigation surveys. The literature review is used to set up the requirements for the monitoring system. Furthermore, the literature is used to survey the equipment that has been used by researchers and the type of measurements conducted.

In Chapter 3, the results of Chapter 2 are combined with an external framework to describe the research aim and objectives of the work reported in this thesis. Using an acoustic array for the monitoring task at the wind turbines for a spatial filtering capability is described together with the aims of data acquisition and data analysis. This part also includes the description of the five phases of the research project.

In Chapter 4, the array system development and testing are explained. All parts contained in the systems are described in detail and evaluated for their suitability in the array. This includes the protective membrane development needed for long-term outdoor measurements. The design procedure and results were published in *Applied Acoustics* [1] in advance of this thesis. The manufactured array is evaluated for its acoustic and spatial filtering performance. In the last part of this chapter, the wind park application with the chosen parameters is described.

In Chapter 5, the performed analysis and the results are presented. Noise emissions analyses with different sensor combinations were made. The measured signals from the wind park are compared to a standard wind turbine noise analysis procedure. Furthermore, the array recordings are combined in an adaptive blade position tracking approach. This enables blade signal monitoring in changing wind conditions.

A summary of the outcomes and findings as well as probable future developments are provided in Chapter 6.

Figure 2 summarises the milestones of this project. They are described by different development stages. The first stage is the developed hardware components and their assembly. The second describes the microphone array simulation, engineering, and manufacturing. The third stage

describes the wind park measurement campaign design and wind park array application and, the last stage describes the acoustic data analysis developments. Figure 2 also shows the five major achievements of the project. All the stages are described in detail in the following chapters.

The developed array monitoring hardware achieved the required performance parameters. The acoustic parameters were achieved by the microphone units used in the array, by acquiring sound samples over the required 48 kHz band which includes all the frequency response components. The array achieved the required spatial filtering performance of 5 m x 5 m acoustic grid resolution at the wind turbine in the frequency range >1.5 kHz. The developed protective membrane provided the needed array robustness for over 9 weeks of wind park application. The recording duration outperformed the required 4 weeks of wind park application to record 76 hours of acoustic data.

Figure 2: Research journey with the milestones during deployment and the major project achievements from different project sections

Recorded wind park data were analysed for dependency on the wind direction during recording. The fixed position recordings were evaluated in contrast to multi-position recordings. Both approaches can provide sufficient data for noise load measurements of wind turbines, although the fixed position recording is significantly dependent on changing wind conditions in the wind park. The results from the analysis show the dependency of the noise load from the wind turbine orientation to the recording position. Additionally, the recorded data were used to develop a spatial filtering algorithm. The developed algorithm processes the positions of the wind turbine blades in the prevailing wind conditions and was evaluated against the measured wind turbine data. The results show that the blade positions depend on turbine orientation and can be successfully estimated. The noise emissions can also be explained in terms of wind influences and a resulting sound wave drift.

The achieved scientific results were summarised into the main achievements and contributions to science can be summarised as follows:

- An in-depth understanding of a protective membrane for MEMS microphones regarding a consistent, validated empirical model, design guidelines and manufacturing
- Development of a robust microphone array for wind turbine emission monitoring in terms of frequency response, spatial filtering resolution and mechanical structure with the following subsystems:
 - A digital microphone unit with a processing unit
 - A mechanical array structure optimized for wind park application
- A first acoustic array dataset with 76 hours recording time from a wind park accompanying environmental and turbine operation data has been produced
- Acoustic wind turbine monitoring procedure for data measured with a microphone array at a fixed position in a wind park over an extended period has been developed
- An automated spatial filtering algorithm for wind turbine blade position estimation for blade signature monitoring has been developed and proposed

Chapter 2 State of the Art

2.1 Abstract

This Chapter reviews the literature and available hardware solutions for the research questions posed in Chapter 1. The results of the analysis are further used as a basis for the methods and the research procedure developed in Chapter 3. This Chapter is separated into reviews regarding acoustic measurements in wind parks and reviews regarding technical analysis results developed in this Chapter will be transferred into the requirements for the hardware development. This Chapter develops the current State of the Art in the research area. Therefore, different methods of wind turbine monitoring with acoustic monitoring hardware are analysed.

2.2 Wind turbine monitoring

Wind turbines emit mechanical and aerodynamical noise. As explained in Chapter 1, monitoring of acoustic noise sources from a wind turbine is important for maintenance, failure prediction and, to understand and minimise environmental noise pollution. The recorded noise can be used to determine the conditions of the emitting pieces of the wind turbine. Measured noise from wind turbines can be used to predict noise emissions that can lead to wind park noise control measures. Multiple aspects of monitoring approaches at wind turbines are conducted in this Section, differentiating between acoustic arrays system, measurements performed in wind parks and the analysis methods of sounds from wind turbines.

2.2.1 Acoustic monitoring array systems

Microphone arrays, also called acoustic arrays or acoustic antennas, are a well-established procedure for sampling incoming sound fields with multiple sensors. They work by recording the sound field at defined positions with microphones and use the geometry of the array to apply spatial filtering. The spatially recorded sound field enables sound sources to be assigned to their point of emission.

There is an increasing number of MEMS microphone-based arrays that have been developed in the past 10 years. Different manufacturers provide microphone array products with a wide range of designs and applications. They are typically handheld battery-powered devices offered by [16], [17], [19]–[22], with smaller sizes up to 50 cm in diameter. Larger arrays are designed to be mounted on tripods [18], [23], [24] with sizes up to 150 cm. These are mainly used in laboratory setups with frequency ranges down to 410 Hz depending on the allowed noise level. In addition to the development of MEMS-based arrays, the separate data acquisition units described in [25], [26] have less importance in modern devices and are directly integrated into newly developed arrays.

Robust arrays for outdoor field usage are only found in research projects carried out by [11], [27]. They were engineered with analogue microphones and have data acquisition units. Both hardware approaches were built with individual microphones placed on the ground. With this transport and reorientation of the array are complicated. Additionally, these arrays are not protected against accidental changes of microphone positions. Investigations with commercial arrays were also found [12], [14], [28], these had to be made in suitable weather conditions due to the lack of weather protection. Due to the lack of suitable weather protection, the durations of the data collections turned out to be short. This is a problem because extreme conditions and failures are more likely to happen during harsh weather and high winds.

In conclusion, there is a need for a robust outdoor array that can be deployed in the field for autonomous and continuous noise monitoring. This array should consider the usage of digital components to benefit from the recent improvements in signal processing, power consumption and package size.

2.2.1.1 Acoustic arrays in wind park applications

Previous publications applying acoustic arrays in wind parks were based on ground-based microphone arrays and small mobile microphone arrays. Research results from continuous measurement longer than one month recorded with an acoustic array have not been published in open literature. In this section, publications on wind turbine array investigations are reviewed to establish the current state of the science.

Oerlemans and López [11] described the use of an array consisting of 152 analogue microphones on a platform about 58 m away from a wind turbine (GAMESA G58 [29]) upwind. The beamforming results of 35 measurements of noise from wind turbines in five different wind speeds, from 5.5 m/s to 10.5 m/s, and with a duration of 30 seconds have been provided. The authors found the sound pressure level (SPL) of the blades increases faster with increased wind speeds than the sound level from the nacelle. Spectra of three differently treated blades were shown by the authors. There is a reduction in SPL of the untreated blade against the tripped blade of up to 7 dB for lower frequencies and of up to 4 dB for frequencies above 2 kHz. The results show the acoustic parameters depend on the treatment and surface finish of the blades and clean blades have lower noise emissions.

Buck et al. [27] present the development of an array designed for measurements. The authors required a weatherproof array. The array shape was designed based on a flat laying array with analogue microphones. The influence of different seasons on the array performance is described. The acoustic maps are analysed with different algorithms and optimization methods. It is shown that an acoustic image correction for the air movement influences with atmospheric models helps with more accurate noise position processing.

Simley [30] describes an array developed for wind turbine applications. The hardware is evaluated in the wind park and measurements are provided. The application of beamforming algorithms to array data and the difficulties with field calibration of a large flat array were described.

Ramachandran et al. [12], [28] provided results of investigations of a small compact array in a wind park. The application of a planar portable array [31] at a 1.5 MW wind turbine shows the ability to separate the sound sources. The nacelle and the blade emissions are part of this investigation. Sources above 1 kHz were able to be located with this size of array, lower frequency sources could not be covered with this size microphone arrays.

In conclusion research findings published open literature are based on measurements conducted with stationary ground-based arrays using individually placed microphones. Furthermore, the investigations with a small (<1 m diameter) planar array show limitations in the source resolution at frequencies below 1 kHz. The operations of wind turbines were recorded in short periods. An applicable solution for long-term coverage of wind turbine sounds was not found.

Ground-based arrays lay flat on the ground and are placed on sound reflective surfaces. The array microphones are placed individually without any structural connection and are connected via cables. This microphone arrangement is focused on one single wind turbine and a setup for a different turbine requires a full disassembly. This design approach requires specific circumstances in the field, e.g., flat ground in the required direction at the turbine, with less flexibility in the array positions. Obstacles or active agriculture are often found in the surrounding of wind parks.

The development of array hardware in this research project is designed to be a transportable solution. Therefore, a system design with a mechanical structure housing the needed microphones is developed in Chapter 4. With this approach, the setup and focus alignment is possible at the recording site with multiple turbines in the field of view. Like the found publications the newly developed array will contain a central data collection and computing unit. This unit will receive

and process the incoming signals from every microphone and enables synchronised signal channel storage and processing of source positions with beamforming algorithms.

2.2.2 Acoustic data recordings in wind parks

Acoustic emission surveys at wind turbines (WT) are made since the wind turbines are installed onshore and people found concerns about noise emissions. Countries like Germany require acoustic mentoring during the wind park planning, construction and at the beginning of operations [32]. Acoustic data recordings published in other publications [33]–[37] are based on the analysis of acoustic emissions from wind turbines for fault detection and condition monitoring purposes. Noise monitoring supplies information on potential defects of a wind turbine and ideally supplies the history of data relevant to the specific problem found. For the review of literature, the following points were chosen for publication evaluation and description:

- Wind turbine power and height: The height and the corresponding power of a wind turbine is a measure of their potential noise emission and is a key parameter for the comparison of noise levels between different turbine types
- Total Duration of signal recording: Is a direct indication for the database used in the publications data analysis
- Analysis method: Differentiation between the applied signal analysis
 - Spatial filtering: Applied algorithms to separate noise sources at the turbine
 - Spectral analysis: Applied analysis in the frequency domain and plotted the results with a frequency relation
 - Level-based analysis: Applied analysis based on noise levels processed from the recorded signals
- Used measurement equipment: The differentiation of the used equipment with their parameters and number of recording channels was chosen to evaluate the presented results for spatial signal assignment and analysis performance

- Sampling frequency: Differentiation between the capabilities of the used equipment
- Secondary measured parameters: This parameter was chosen for the differentiation of conditions that the recordings were performed in and to evaluate the requirement for addition sensor equipment
- Results and comments: Findings and results highlighted by the author

If one point was not described in the publication the column was left blank.

The review of publications in Table 1 supplies an overview of methods for measuring acoustic signals at wind turbines.

A combination of an array system with continuous operations was not found in open literature. Arrays were used only for discrete formulated questions and with short durations of recordings in wind parks. This gap of research will be filled by the proposed system to be developed as part of this project, with a solution of automated spatial filtered signal processing. The system developed in this work includes 64 microphone channels operating in a wind farm with a duration of 76 hours. as shown in Figure 3. Thus, it reaches a sweet spot in terms of recording duration and the number of array channels, the development process and the design evaluation are described in detail in Section 4.4.2. The proposed system will be used together with other environmental sensors to differentiate between weather and wind conditions during recording, which is crucial for correlation between occurring noise and the operational conditions.

Figure 3: Duration of acoustic noise recording and the number of channels from publications in Table 1; Data labels correspond to the number of the publication in the table. Number 10 covers the number 3; number 17 covers number 16; and number 9 covers number 7 due to the same data points

No.	Publication	WT power /height	Total duration	Equipment / sampling frequency	Analysis/filtering method	Secondary measured parameters	Results/ comments
1	S. Oerlemans, J. G. Schepers, G. Guidati, and S. Wagner, 'Experimental demonstration of wind turbine noise reduction through optimized airfoil shape and trailing-edge serrations', National Aerospace Laboratory, pp. 2–5, 2001. [38]	Scale rotor / -	Not specified	4x4 m 136 channel microphone array / -	Noise image with specific frequency ranges	Wind tunnel speeds between 11 and 16 m/s	Noise reduction by an optimized air foil shape is possible, evaluated in scale format, Relevant for this work in the perspective of the applied algorithms in the acoustic data
2	W. Bray and R. James, 'Dynamic measurements of wind turbine acoustic signals, employing sound quality engineering methods considering the time and frequency sensitivities of human perception', Noise-Con, 2011.[39]	1.5 MW / -	Several 100 minutes in two days	Binaural artificial head with two ½” microphones 48 kHz 24bit	Level analysis in octave bands	Tree and shrubs between test sight and turbines	Signals of wind turbines are presented as time series of SPL and spectrograms; general turbine signals are plotted and tagged with events or source types
3	S. Lee, K. Kim, W. Choi, and S. Lee, 'Annoyance caused by amplitude modulation of wind turbine noise', Noise Control Engineering Journal, vol. 59, no. 1, p. 38, 2011.[40]	1.5 MW / -	Three days	B&K 4190 sound level meter 24 kHz	Time and frequency filtering for hearing test	Wind speed varied from 3 m/ s to 14 m/ s	Noise annoyance increases with the amplitude modulation of wind turbine noise
4	T. Boczar, T. Malec, and D. Wotzka, 'Studies on infrasound noise emitted by wind turbines of large power', Acta Physica Polonica A, vol. 122, no. 5, pp. 850–853, 2012.[41]	2 MW/90 m	Minutes	B & K, type 4190 1.2 Hz to 10 kHz	Spectral analysis of low frequencies	Temp., hum., pressure., Wind speed 1 to 8 m/s	Infrasound noise levels were below the thresholds of human hearing, the provided levels were weighted with the G weighting curve for low frequency recordings
5	Stuart Bradley, Torben Mikkelsen, Mathew Legg, and Sabine von Hünerbein, 'PRECISION MEASUREMENTS OF WIND TURBINE NOISE USING A LARGE APERTURE MICROPHONE ARRAY', p. 11, 2016. [13]	- / 35 m	Multiple 5 minutes	40m array - 42 microphones sampled at 20 kHz	Spatial filtering with 1 m resolution Spectral doppler analysis	Meteorological data from mast	Blade motion generates a doppler shift of the recordable noise emissions, artificial sources were placed on the blades and measured, referring for the need of instrument artefacts movement

6	S. Buck, J. Readman, P. Moriarty, and S. Palo, 'Acoustic Array Development for Wind Turbine Noise Characterization'. Nov-2013. [27]	600 kW / 36,4 m	380 x 45 seconds ~ 4:30 hours	63 microphone spiral array + B & K, type 4190 reference	Spatial filtering	Atmospheric condition data	Measured with recommendations of international standard IEC 61400-11, Wind turbine tips emit the most noise during tower passing at 3.2 kHz
7	S. Oerlemans, P. Sijtsma, and B. Méndez López, 'Location and quantification of noise sources on a wind turbine', Journal of Sound and Vibration, vol. 299, no. 4-5, pp. 869-883, Feb. 2007. [8]	850 kW / 53.5 m	110 acoustic measurement x 30 seconds	horizontal 148 microphones array sampled at 51.2kHz	Spatial filtering Spectral analysis of specific parts	Wind speeds between 6 and 10 m/s	Blade noise was dominant, Roughness of the blade surface changed the noise emissions
8	S. Oerlemans, 'Wind turbine noise: primary noise sources', Apr. 2014. [42]	2.3 MW / 100m	20 minutes	horizontal 148 microphones array sampled at 51.2kHz	Spatial, spectral, level	Wind speed	Highest noise levels between 315 Hz and 1250 Hz, results indicated that the dominant noise source for typical modern large wind turbines is broadband trailing edge noise from the outer part of the blades, Acoustic source on the blades (800 Hz)
9	S. Oerlemans and B. Méndez López, 'Acoustic Array Measurements on full Scale Wind Turbine', 2005.[11]	850 kW / 53.5 m	110 acoustic measurement x 30 seconds	148 microphones horizontal microphone array; sampled at 51.2kHz	Spatial filtering	wind speeds between 6 and 10 m/s	Hub and blade noise were compared, blades are dominant, practically all noise (emitted to the ground) is produced during the downward movement of the blades
10	S. E. Ambrose, S. E. Ambrose, G. F. Road, and R. W. Rand, 'Falmouth, Massachusetts wind turbine infrasound and low frequency noise measurements', inter.noise, 2012.[43]	1.65 MW / -	3 days of observation	Type 1 microphone with 24-bit AD conversion	Spectral analysis up to 1 kHz, Level analysis	-	The dBA measurement does not correlate directly to human complaints, health symptoms were stronger indoors where dBA levels were significantly lower

11	S. Buck, S. Oerlemans, and S. Palo, 'Experimental characterization of turbulent inflow noise on a full-scale wind turbine', <i>Journal of Sound and Vibration</i> , vol. 385, pp. 219–238, Dec. 2016.[44]	2.3 MW / 80 m	50 h	Acoustic ground ring 12 Microphones	Spatial spectral	Wind speed	Sound pressure levels can be affected by turbulences as much as 7 dB, the authors show the dependency of noise levels to the turbine orientations, these results will be used for this works analysis
12	R. C. Ramachandran, G. Raman, and R. P. Dougherty, 'Wind turbine noise measurement using a compact microphone array with advanced deconvolution algorithms', <i>Journal of Sound and Vibration</i> , vol. 333, no. 14, pp. 3058–3080, Jul. 2014. [45]	1.5 MW / 85 m	Not specified	24 Microphones array	Spatial, Spectral	Wind speed	A compact microphone array is sufficient to perform detailed studies on wind turbines, Blade noise is dominant
13	N. A. B. Monarca et al., 'Acoustic Characterization Of Wind Farms In Chile: Wind Turbine Noise Measurements Throughout The Country', p. 13, Aug. 2018. [46]	1.5 to 5 MW / varies	Multiple weeks and 4 h discrete	30 microphones array and single level meters	Spatial, Spectral, level	Wind speed	Acoustic camera works better for direct investigations, emissions can vary within 15 dB in one day due to weather condition change
14	M. Björkman, 'Long time measurements of noise from wind turbines', <i>Journal of Sound and Vibration</i> , vol. 277, no. 3, pp. 567–572, 2004. [47]	Not specified / -	2 years	Sound level meters	Spectral, Level	Meteorological data	The wind speed and operating condition of the wind turbine have complex influence on the soundscape, and this is usually not described by the simple A-weighted noise indices
15	H. Möller and C. S. Pedersen, 'Low-frequency noise from large wind turbines', <i>The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America</i> , vol. 129, no. 6, pp. 3727–3727, 2011. [48]	3.6 MW / -	Not specified	Sound level meters	Spectral, level	Wind speed	The relative number of low frequencies is higher with larger turbines Measured in accordance with IEC 61400–11
16	enveco, 'Schallimmissionsprognose Windenergieprojekt Beverungen-Twerberg'. Aug-2014. [49]	2.5 MW / 85 m	Not specified	Sound level meters	Level	Wind speed	Measured in accordance with IEC 61400–11

17	C. Hu, R. Albertani, and R. M. Suryan, 'Wind turbine sensor array for monitoring avian and bat collisions: Wind turbine sensor array for monitoring avian and bat collisions', <i>Wind Energy</i> , vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 255–263, Apr. 2018. [50]	1.5 Mw and 600 kW / -	Not specified	Acoustic microphone (10 Hz to 20 kHz) and acceleration sensors	Spectral, level	Not specified	Vibration sensors are suitable for blade impact detection, the authors developed a blade impact system with vibrational sensors at the nacelle and showed test data in spectrographs,
18	Bayrisches Landesamt für Umweltschutz, 'Langzeit-Geräuschemissionsmessung an einer WEA'. Jan-2000. [51]	1 MW / 60 m	1 year	Sound level meters	level	Wind speed and direction	German regulation for noise emissions, providing maximum noise levels for day and night operation
19	B. Zajamšek, K. L. Hansen, C. J. Doolan, and C. H. Hansen, 'Characterisation of wind farm infrasound and low-frequency noise', <i>Journal of Sound and Vibration</i> , vol. 370, pp. 176–190, May 2016. [52]	3 MW / 90 m	15 days	Measurement microphone	spectral	Wind speed and direction	Signals of an operating and not operating wind turbine are compared in spectra, comparison of the background noise and wind turbine noise at different measurement positions relative to the turbine are presented
20	Oerlemans, S., Fisher, M., Maeder, T., & Kögler, K. (2009). Reduction of Wind Turbine Noise Using Optimized Airfoils and Trailing-Edge Serrations. <i>AIAA Journal</i> , 47(6), 1470–1481. https://doi.org/10.2514/1.38888 [53]	2.3 MW / 100 m	600x 30 sec = 5 h	Acoustic flat ground array with 51 Microphones	Spatial spectral	Wind speed/direction, turbine data	Individual blade noise source identification was performed; Up- and downwind conditions were recorded with a fixed array position

Table 1: Publication in wind turbine noise emission surveys

2.2.3 Wind turbine acoustic analysis

Turbine parts generate different unique sound patterns in time and frequency domains, compare S. Oerlemans et al. [8]. The main influencing factor of the emitted signature is the rotational turbine speed and its emitted vibrational frequencies. The rotational speed is a result of the wind speed the turbine is operating in but is limited to a maximum speed by pitch control.

Noise recorded from a position outside a wind turbine is dominated by aerodynamic sources. These are mostly emitted from the moving blades [54] with three different sources of noise-producing mechanisms. Low frequency noise (typically 20 - 100 Hz) is generated by the moving blades and blades producing interference with the tower and wind. This phenome is present three times per full rotation, due to the three-blade turbine design. The blades' in-flow turbulence sound [42] is generated by pressure fluctuations around the blades. There is also broadband airfoil noise [55] that is generated by airflow over the surfaces. In addition, mechanical noise sources are located inside the turbine's nacelle [8] including sources like gearboxes, generators, blade and tower drives, cooling systems, and hydraulic components. The mechanical noise travels as structural vibrations to the nacelle housing and is detectable as surface movements from the outside. The fan noise [55] is generated at the tower base and, the mechanical noises are present in specific wind directions and turbine orientations compared to the array. The emitted noise levels of wind turbines can generate in specific wind conditions a noise level of concern at close by residents. These sound levels are mainly generated by aerodynamic emission and can reach peak levels of 100 dbSPL [39].

The state-of-the-art acoustic noise emission measurements are performed with single-channel microphone recorders. Those recordings flow the standard IEC 61400-11 [10] and are mainly interested in sound levels and octave band analysis of the overall turbine emissions. The limiting factors of environmental and operational conditions described by the standard reduce the applicability and significance of actual wind turbine operation and resulting emission. Additionally, does this approach have a reduced dimension of information since there is no connection between the recorded signals and

its source of emission. A longer recording time and source positioning are the limiting factors of current standardised recordings.

2.3 Research elements of novelty in system design and data measurement campaign

The analysis of existing research approaches in the literature and the available measurement hardware found the research and knowledge gap of microphone arrays for outdoor usage for long-term applications or acoustic monitoring purposes. This research aims toward the operation in the spot shown in Figure 3. Here a system with 50 to 100 microphones for spatial resolution and an continuous recording time for months would fill that gap. It addresses the gaps in available systems that are applicable for turbine noise emissions. Noise source monitoring at turbines with an adaptation to the environmental influences was not found in the analysis and is one objective of this project. Therefore, the combination of auxiliary wind sensors and the acoustic array signals is used to generate a novel approach to wind turbine noise emission observations. These approaches are made possible by continuous multichannel recording with the tailored recording system developed. The array system developed should be portable with the ability to continuously record acoustic data in the wind park. The lack of ruggedised microphone array systems for outdoor continuous measurement led to the design of a novel method to protect array microphones against water and dust as a part of this work. This analysis leads into the next Chapter where the project approaches are described in more detail.

2.4 Conclusion

The analysis made in this Chapter shows that there is a need for research in the field of acoustic measurement methods and equipment for wind turbines. It was found that spatial mapping of acoustic sources is required for detailed noise emission measurements at wind turbines. Published literature on wind turbine recording with a single channel lack in spatial resolution and are unusable for the

combination of turbine observation and noise monitoring. The analysed publications showed the lack of the continuous use of transportable arrays for wind park applications.

Chapter 3 Aims and Research Approach

3.1 Abstract

This Chapter describes the objectives and the research approach for this work. Research aims are derived from the literature in the previous Chapter and from the requirements of the wind park application. Wind Park requirements are developed in this Chapter based on previous measurements and the geometry at wind turbines. The approach applied to fulfil the research aims is described in detail and parameters for their evaluation are developed in this chapter.

3.2 Research aims

The project's research aim is the development and evaluation of acoustic array systems for a wind park monitoring operation with a focus on noise monitoring and turbine signature processing. It is driven by the hypothesis that it is possible to develop a microphone array that is deployable in all-year round for continuous wind park monitoring operations. The system would provide wind turbine part sound signal and signature assignment, background noise mask-out during investigations, and general noise suppression which leads to an improved monitoring result compared to existing single-channel acoustic wind park monitoring equipment.

Developing acoustic monitoring hardware capable of recording noise emissions that can be used to spatially identify sound sources from turbine parts is crucial for a detailed understanding is one of the

aims of the project. An attached signal processing and spatial filtering pipeline is another aim of this research. The combination of both, the hardware and effective data processing utilisation is necessary for the evaluation of the primary objective.

The primary objective contains sub-aims that include outdoor monitoring hardware development, optimal experimental data acquisition, and algorithmic adaptation to wind turbine usage. The sub-aims are described in detail in the following paragraphs.

3.2.1 Monitoring system aims

The aims of the monitoring system development are guided by the acoustic recording performance, the robustness for outdoor usage, and a reliable continuous operation. These requirements are covered in the development process and were evaluated for their performance. They were developed from the wind park application and presented at the ICSV24[2] and, parts of the requirements are as presented in Table 2. The sampling frequency is required for the spatial filtering in the acoustic grid to eliminate the need for processed subsamples. It is processed with the geometry of the array placed in front of the turbine with is a distance of up to 200 m and the dimensions of the acoustic grid that covers the swept area of the blade. With a required acoustic image resolution of 5m source separation distance the minimum audio sampling frequency, according to the explanation in [2], is 5473 Hz needed for the signal delay. Additionally, to the geometrical consideration, there is the spectrum of noise emitted from wind turbines, here there is the spectrum recorded and presented in Figure 8. The highest frequency recorded was 9 kHz. Together with the lowest frequency of 20 Hz it sets the limits and the required minimum sampling frequency, due to the Nyquist theorem, to 18 kHz. In addition to the sampling frequency, the resolution requirement was set to 24 bits to increase the number of noise levels distinguishable with the microphones. The general environmental requirements were deducted from the prevalent conditions in the wind park.

Table 2: Requirement for the acoustic monitoring system

Required parameter	Value
Minimum sampling frequency	18 kHz
Sample resolution	24 bits
Microphone frequency range	20 Hz to 9 kHz
Temperature range of operation	-20 to +50 °C
Relative humidity range of operation	0 to 100 %RH

The system should contain multiple microphones, although the design should be portable and should withstand environmental conditions in the field. The hardware should be ruggedised for field deployment to conduct measurements continuously subject to power availability.

The aim of this project is the development of the array system with the described acoustic and system properties. Fulfilling these the system

3.2.2 Data recording aims

For reliable determination of the wind turbine operational condition or a potential irregular noise from a turbine the data acquisition should include the wind turbine operational conditions during normal and extreme wind conditions. This includes acoustic recordings in all directions relative to the wind direction within multiple wind speeds. This data collection aims to include reference sensors for wind speed and direction outside of the turbine. This will allow correlations between the turbine's operational parameters and the wind sensors data. With the data collected in this way, the wind turbine system can be examined in detail for effects on acoustic emissions. In total, the recording system should remain longer than 4 weeks in the wind park to collect data under multiple environmental conditions.

3.2.3 Data analytical aims

The analytics based on the wind park recordings applies signal processing and spatially filtering monitoring to the wind turbine noise emissions. The aim is to develop a robust analytical signal processing pipeline that adapts to different wind and environmental conditions. The main goal is to adapt

the spatial filtering algorithms to wind park conditions to increase capabilities for future wind park monitoring. This adaptation would enable a wide field of additional long-term investigations on emission changes or anomaly detection.

3.3 Research approach and study design

The research approach of how to apply continuous acoustic monitoring with a spatial signal assignment at a wind turbine is described in this section. The developments are driven by the requirements to apply the array at the test site and are data-driven since a lot of reference data are necessary for signal processing pipeline adaptation.

3.3.1 Research approach

The research approach is based on the question of research presented in the introduction:

How can an acoustic array monitoring system be applied continuously in a wind park for noise monitoring and noise source localization on wind turbines?

This question is divided into multiple sub-questions which are answered in Chapters 4 and 5.

- How can an acoustic array development be made suitable for wind park operation?
- How can a continuous microphone array recording deliver comparable noise monitoring results to the international standard for wind turbine noise recording according to IEC 61400-11[10]?
- How are the spatial filtering capabilities adaptable for continuous wind turbine monitoring?

3.3.2 Experimental design

The experimental setup, as shown in Figure 4, in this thesis is designed to examine the microphone array application for acoustic wind park monitoring. The recorded signals are evaluated and algorithmically combined with data from auxiliary wind sensors.

The experimental setup consists of a microphone array, a data acquisition unit, and auxiliary wind sensors. The microphone array is developed with wind park requirements and state-of-the-art design approaches and hardware components. Array characterisation and the characterisation of components in the array are described in detail in Section 4.5. Further is the array application in the wind park described in that Section, the position selection is crucial for the collection of noise data of the wind turbine. The noise data should be covering the operational conditions in the different wind situations and the placement should guarantee the ability to record turbine sound which is distance and wind direction dependent. The experimental design includes auxiliary wind sensors, these sensors provide the data to evaluate the wind field with direction and speed and the related sound drift. In addition to the wind data, the wind turbine operational data is also available. For this research, the wind turbine orientation (azimuth angle), the blades' pitch angle and the rotational speed with the reached output power are relevant and are available. The orientation is relevant because it is related to the wind direction and the noise emissions differ with the different orientations. The blade pitch can be seen as an overload provision system since it is used to cut the rotational speed in high wind speeds for structural protection. This influences again the acoustics and noise emission of the turbine during operations. Further is the rotational speed with the output power data stored to analysis the effects on how much the noise is increased by rising numbers. By recording both the wind and turbine data in parallel, the wind and turbine data can be mutually verified for correctness. Thus, considerations for future projects can be made regarding whether both data sources must always be available. This will become relevant when the operational data are not available in a project and simpler ground-operated wind sensors are applied.

The design and manufacturing of the microphone array for the continuous wind park operation are necessary since there is no suitable hardware available at the start of the project. Design decisions and the array's performance are evaluated with dedicated measurements in the system development section to ensure the needed array performance level.

3.3.3 Data collection campaign design

The design of the data collection campaign considers the duration of wind park recording to be over multiple weeks to record emission data from different wind turbine azimuth angles with a fixed positioned array. With this approach, it will guarantee that wind speeds and directions will vary in the duration of the recordings.

The system under test (SUT), the wind turbine in the wind park, is free from any other influences other than the wind speed and direction. If the turbine is rotating, the generated power is linked to those two contributing factors. Noise emissions are considered the output value of interest in the Design of the Experiment and are related to the turbine's rotational speed. This factor is measured by external sensors in fixed positions without influencing the turbine operation. The general setup approach is illustrated in Figure 4. The array position will be chosen to cover the whole turbine structure with its field of view. With the resulting distance, the spatial filtering acoustic grid will be superimposed on the swept area (marked with the blue circle) and the turbine tower. The grid is the base for the following spatial filtering processing. The SUTs internal operational parameters, e.g., turbine power output, pitch angle and orientation, are stored with the wind direction and speed data and are fed into the data analysis. These data are crucial to compare the acoustic results with the turbine mode of operations and the prevailing wind conditions to deduce the connection parameters.

Figure 4: Array setup approach at one wind turbine, the superimposed rectangular grid is illustrating the acoustic grid applied for spatial filtering of the turbine sound emissions, the dimensions in x and y are chosen to cover the sound sources of interest

The measurement in the wind park application will consider the IEC 61400 [56] standard as a reference for position and wind speed windows around the wind turbine. The standard IEC 61400-11:2013 [10] describes a narrow-allowed measurement area relative to the wind turbine and wind direction, compare [10, Fig. 5] with an acoustic recording device downwind together with the meteorological sensor position outside of possible turbulences area. In addition to the downwind configuration, there are three more positions allowed for the upwind and two side wind configurations. This reduces the number of possible measurement positions for a continuous recording campaign within the standard's limitations. The application of the developed measuring hardware in the wind park is described in Section 4.7.

The experimental data collection is planned in the research wind park located in Hamburg-Curslack. In the wind park a wind turbine of type Nordex Delta 117/3MW [57] is chosen as a data source. The turbine type is the newest model available in the wind park and represents a 3 MW mean onshore power rating in Germany from 2017 to 2020 [7]. Data collection campaigns are designed during two different seasonal conditions for a wide coverage of conditions and temperatures. The turbine emission and the array performance in different environmental conditions are investigated. Each campaign includes the

collection of acoustic data, a video stream, and an external anemometer for reference wind field description.

3.3.4 Data analysis

The data analysis approach is to generate more parameters that can be used to describe the operational condition of the turbines. For this purpose, the data recorded with the developed system are evaluated together with the turbine and wind sensor data. The first analysis is designed to correlate and combine measured quantities for data overview purposes. The second analysis is adapting the spatial filtering for blade signals to different wind conditions during the recording.

The first data analysis takes the recorded microphone data for noise level analysis from one fixed position close by the wind turbine. It is examined whether with the one position over a long measuring period results can be produced which correspond to the standard IEC 61400-11 [10]. The standard on the other hands requires multiple position changes around a wind turbine in specific wind conditions to perform valuable noise level measurements at wind turbines. The idea is to overcome the wait for the required conditions and use continuous recordings. Those continuous data have the potential to cover all needed conditions without any manual intervention. In the end, recorded data is analysed based on the noise signals and are compared to the required parameters from IEC 61400-11 [10]. This approach is described in Section 5.2.

The second data analysis and algorithm development are adapting the source positioning to compensate environmental and turbine influences. The adapted spatial filtering approach is used to design a blade signature detection. The spatial filter approach is needed to adapt the position for optimal blade signature tracking in different wind fields. The algorithm uses the acoustic data in combination with auxiliary data of wind sensors and the wind turbine to evaluate the processed blade positions. The processed positions of the blade should be within reasonable margins compared to the actual wind turbine orientation. The development, signal processing and results are presented in Section 5.3.

3.4 Conclusion

In this chapter, the different aspects of this work and the planned procedure were described. Therefore, in Chapter 2 found existing solutions were translated, with the new project approach, into aims for the new development. This includes the three aspects of the monitoring system, data recording and data analysis. Furthermore, the aims were transferred into the research approach. Here the general Question of research was divided into three, each one covering one aspect of the aims. This approach will be used in the upcoming Chapters 4 and 5 to develop the required array hardware together with the wind park data recording and data analysis.

Chapter 4 Experimental setup and system development

4.1 Abstract

This Chapter describes the development process and performance evaluation of the hardware components required in this thesis. The overall development goal is to set up and apply an acoustic array in the wind park. The array is thereby divided into individual hardware components, which have been developed, manufactured, and tested. The analyses from the previous chapters were considered about the application and the state-of-the-art. Further, the developed requirements were taken into account and were the base for the selection of hardware components. In the last part of this chapter, the developed array is applied in the wind park, together with the required auxiliary sensors. The wind park applied array provides the acoustic data for the analyses in the following Chapter 5.

4.2 Acoustic source separation in wind parks with microphone arrays

Source separation of noise sources at the wind turbine are a crucial aspect of the work and enable more detailed investigation at the turbines. The concept of noise recording device for wind turbines in a wind park applies a multichannel microphone array to the sound field emitted in the wind park. The sound

source separation is applied to assign signals to various parts of the wind turbine. The recording array spatially samples the incoming sound pressure field at defined microphone positions. Conversely, this allows the source position to be inferred from the different positions and the simultaneous time sampling via runtime differences from each source to each microphone in the array. Delay and sum spatial filtering algorithms in the frequency domain are applied to the sampled array signals for the sound emission position reconstruction in the array's area of focus. An example of the application of spatial filtering to wind turbine emission is shown in Figure 4. The coloured part is showing the spatial filtering results of the blade tips from a selected frequency band. It is processed on a defined grid and the plotted as a heatmap over the image of the wind turbine. This approach provides the observation of the whole wind turbine as well as the ability to focus on specific parts of the turbine. In addition to the heatmap optical illustration, time signals processed for every position in the grid are available for other downstream investigations. Acoustic recordings of sound fields with spatially distributed microphones assign signals to discrete sources allowing, background sources to be eliminated from the output time signal.

Figure 5: Typical spatial filtering application at wind turbine with a grid; upwind results of a selected frequency range of the blade emissions

The monitoring system used remained in the wind park during the measurement campaign. The array system continuously records sound data at the test site for off-site processing. Continuous monitoring

of acoustic sources at wind turbines requires a robust microphone array. The robustness is crucial for long-term outdoor wind park applications and must combine water- and dust protection of all hardware components.

The concept is using a single microphone array in a wind park. The monitoring system records the sound emissions from up to 4 wind turbines in a range of 300 m and turbine blades and nacelles in the postprocessing phase. With this approach, the following key parameters can be achieved:

- An installation in the wind park in under an hour
- Flexible position adaptation to changes in vegetation or research approach
- Investigations on turbine sound emissions
 - Blade signature investigations
 - Nacelle emission investigations
 - Integrated noise emissions from regions or large areas

The array is designed to contain 64 microphone units. The development process of the array structure with the evaluation of the channel number is described in Section 4.4.3. Each microphone unit in the array structure contains multiple microphones together with an accelerometer sensor and digital connections attached to a processing unit, implemented with a microcontroller. This sensor concept allows flexible adaptation to different frequency ranges and requirement changes in upcoming applications in future projects, details of the microphone development are presented in Section 4.4.5. The processing unit can perform sensor fusion, bus conversion, or digital filtering which makes it a powerful hardware platform for future sensing projects.

Spatial filtering of acoustic noise sources is based on the differences in distances between each array microphone and the distances of an artificial acoustic image plane projected onto the wind turbine swept area. The different distances result due to the speed of sound in a time delay of a point source noise at every microphone in the array. The approach is illustrated in Figure 6 with lines showing examples of distances between array microphones and the positions in the acoustic grid. The resulting time delays are translated into sample sifts for each microphone signal and each grid position. For a defined acoustic

grid, the delays needed to process the signals for every position in the grid are processed once from the given geometry and stored in a matrix for signal processing. The delayed signals are processed for the positions and are then summed, the resulting values are divided by the number of microphones in the array. The resulting values can be stored in the acoustic grid, which can then be interpreted as a pixel grid that can be plotted above a camera image. Other than plotting the image the signals from each position can be plotted as a time series for further algorithmic analysis. This whole algorithm is called Delay-and-Sum in the time domain and can also be converted into the frequency domain. Here the signal time shifts are translated into phase shifts of the signal's complex spectrum. The resulting signals of the focused source position in the acoustic grid are amplified against every other grid position. In the application on wind turbines frequency ranges are preselected to search for different turbine parts which emit sound in a specific frequency range. This lets the algorithm search for those parts in the grid and can be used to compensate for atmospheric influences on sound propagation. The focusing on source helps in damping unwanted noise sources, which can be e.g., streets and planes, in the signals and in downstream analysis.

Figure 6: Spatial filtering principal illustration; lines represent the distances between microphone in the array and the grid positions in the acoustic plane; d = distance array to turbine tower; dc = distance array centre acoustic plane centre; x , y axis of the acoustic grid

The signal processing is made in a Python framework. Therefore, general file read and data handling parts were used together with the spatial filtering and beamforming framework Acoular [58]. The Python environment was chosen because of the availability of frameworks, supported file formats, processing speeds, and portability of written scripts. In addition, Python provides advanced data processing and AI development capabilities for future projects based on this work. The used Acoular framework provides implementations of spatial filtering algorithms with parallel processing capabilities. The processing of acoustic images and noise positions is performed on previously recorded and stored array data. Here doses the array record acoustic and optical data in the field and stores them for postprocessing on detached network storage. The postprocessing is implemented with the acoustic array data, the environmental wind data, and the turbine operational data as input. An implementation of an acoustic source separation processing chain is explained in detail in Section 5.2.3 for an adaptation of the acoustic grind based on the turbine orientation. For processing, the input data of all data sources were synchronized and fed into the signal processing chain.

The spatial filtering requires additional data for an effective source processing other than the acoustic array data. There are the microphone positions in the array, the distance from the array to the acoustic grid, and the dimensions and resolution of the grid needed for the delay estimation. These data are measured or are set according to the requirements. Further are the environmental values set according to the measured temperature during the recording. This is considered in the speed of sound which translates into a different delay needed for beam focusing onto grid points. The acoustic grid is set to cover the whole turbine's swept area with a spatial resolution of 5 m and ± 120 m for the x and y dimensions.

An example of the acoustic array data processing with the mentioned functionality is provided in the Appendix B: Adaptive spatial filtering analysis script. In that example code, the acoular functions are described according to their function and usage.

The array system development was performed in multiple steps of vertical integration as described by the multi-domain engineering development V-model [59], shown in Figure 7. The parts Blocks from the

V-Model are represented by the different Sections of Chapter 4, and especially the Hardware development in Section 4.4 follows the shown model. The system design was made with consideration of the requirements described in Section 4.2 and the different structural and electrical components were developed in Section 4.3, both are defined in the V-model by the upper left blocks. The needed test and performance evaluations are presented in 4.5. For the wind park application, a detailed investigation was needed to protect the developed microphone sensing units, this design and development process is described in Section 4.4 and was previously published in Applied Acoustics [1]. The mentioned Sections describe the left testing part of the V-Model. The final test and the wind park application are described in Section 4.6 with the consideration of array positionings and main wind direction in the wind park. All described steps of developments are validated against their individual or system-wide requirements and with that complete the approach of the V-model.

Figure 7: V-model of multi-domain engineering development projects applied to the development of the acoustic array for wind park application

4.3 Multichannel wind turbine monitoring requirements

In the scenario of acoustic array recording in a wind park, the system requirements were deduced from the sound emission of wind turbines, monitoring requirements, and the conditions of operation in a wind park. The observed wind turbine sound emissions frequency range is crucial to the performance of a monitoring system for wind turbines. Thus frequency spectra of wind turbines in Figure 8 under variable conditions have been measured at the beginning of this project and published at the ICSV24 [2] and, were analysed and compared to other studies reported in the open literature [60], [61]. In Figure 6 and published literature relevant sound emissions do contain signal frequencies up to 9 kHz at -90 dB SPL for wind turbines in ground-based recordings. This led to a required frequency range from 20 Hz to 9 kHz for each microphone unit in the array. Recording sound with frequencies below 20 Hz would be beneficial to the analytical process, but there is no available MEMS microphone that covers that frequency range. Other acoustic performance requirements were presented in Table 2 and address the hardware abilities of the sensor units.

Figure 8: Distribution of frequencies of a typical wind turbine emission (author's measurement).

Measured wind turbine Senvion MM100 with 100 m nacelle height and 100 m blade diameter[62]

The wind park monitoring system should achieve a spatial resolution at the wind turbine of Δx and Δy of 5 m, as shown in Figure 9, in the mentioned frequency range. With this array, algorithms can separate two acoustic point sources at the wind turbine with a minimal distance of 5 m if they appear as ideal point sources. In the wind turbine scale, the 5 m spatial filtering accuracy enables a detailed investigation of sources and failures. The wind park monitoring system is supposed to stay in the wind park for an extended period. In this timeframe, no maintenance to the hardware setup should be necessary and the array should withstand the environmental conditions. To achieve this, it is necessary that the array housing is water- and dustproof. Temperatures tolerances from $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ up to $50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ are required to safeguard the operations.

Figure 9: Schematical arrangement of a microphone array at a wind turbine

4.4 Hardware development

4.4.1 Preliminary work

The microphone unit hardware version used in this work is the result of multiple years of development and improvements. The development started with the idea of a multipurpose acoustic sensing unit with the capability to combine multiple units in arrays. The initial version of a fully digital acoustic array recording unit was developed in 2016 [3]. Since then, three development iterations took place. The first two designs include two digital MEMS microphones and a MEMS accelerometer sensor on a single PCB. The digital MEMS microphones MP45DT02 [63] and SPH0641LU4H [64] are soldered to this board together with the acceleration sensor LIS3DSH [65] from ST Microelectronics. Reviewing the test and the performance of the developed board provided sufficient acoustic and processing performance. But the iterated Versions lack in the ability to be mounted in an enclosed array. Installed sensors can record sound signals and the vibrations or movement of the board itself. Onboard sensor data processing and transmission are performed by Atmel microprocessor ATSAMG53 [66]. The sensor units were assessed in different acoustic conditions to determine the frequency behaviour of the manufactured sensors. Figure 10 a) shows this first board developed and manufactured.

Figure 10: Multi-Sensor-Microphone (MSM) board development true to scale; a) first version of the MSM; b) second development with reduced board size and advanced clock control and stability; both boards contain two MEMS microphones (marked with microphone in the top section), microcontroller (central black IC) and acceleration sensor (in between the microcontroller and microphones)

In an array assembly, these sensor units were connected to a central unit which was implemented with an FPGA-Raspberry-Pi combination for parallel data collection and storage. Sensing units were connected via SPI-bus to the central data acquisition and control unit via the bus-master, implemented on the LOGI-PI FPAG platform [67], where the serial data were processed to a parallel data stream of all connected sensing units. In the development, in 2016 the LOGI-PI implementation was the only available FPGA-Raspberry Pi hardware combination available. The combined data were fed as one data packet per sample to the attached Raspberry-Pi [68], where storage and timestamping were made. The chosen system design and hardware were designed for 16 attached microphones and did not include additional performance and connectors for additional microphones.

The second development iteration improved the first in size and clock support stability. It was fully compatible with the previously developed central unit. The acoustic characteristics and sensors were not changed. Figure 10 b) shows the second development iteration in comparison to the first larger PCB of the first version.

The findings, the tested components, and component's interaction from the prototypes were used for the microphone sensor unit development in Section 4.3.5. Thereby the found limitations were analysed regarding the given requirements. Mostly the raised knowledge of system and PCB design and the sensor-controller-integration were considered in the following developments, specific hardware of the central unit and the form-factor were not pursued further. Furthermore, the developed knowledge in MEMS microphone characterization measurements was used in this work.

4.4.2 Array microphone positioning

The array microphone positioning aims to achieve the required spatial resolution of 5 m on the acoustic turbine grid for a wide range of frequencies. This would allow detailed investigation on the positions of different noise sources at the wind turbine. The microphone positioning development is made to acquire the required spatial filtering performance within the applications frequency ranges of 20 Hz to 9 kHz and the distances of operation of 150 m to the wind turbine. The array structure was chosen to consist of strait pipes to achieve high robustness and a stiff structure. This is needed for the transportation ability and to keep the designed microphone positions in strong wind forces with a ridged structure in the field. This design decision limits the possible position to multiple straight lines with a joining central connection piece. The joint central piece is required for the central cable routing and microphone unit synchronization and is not an acoustic design choice, but necessary to store the microphone data.

The positions and the resulting distances between the array microphones directly affect the array spatial filtering performance. The array geometry generated a frequency-dependent filtering behaviour. It is generated by the distances in the array and the resulting main lobe together with existing sidelobes which both are frequency depended [69]. It is the result of different wavelength of incoming sound waves that interact with the distances of microphones in the array geometry. For low-frequency waves with longer wavelengths a large array structure is required for best filtering performance. On the other end of the spectrum do higher frequencies need shorter distances for the best performance. A good filtering performance is indicated by the ability to separate two sources with the same frequency in the acoustic grid. Both performance measures are evaluated by the width of the main lobe at -3dB from its maximum.

The resulting array structure of this development is therefore an optimized compromise for the specific frequency range measured in the wind park.

The design process started with a literature review on the latest algorithms for microphone array design. Sarradj published the current work at the Berlin Beamforming Conference [70], it was used as a reference for the design process in this work. Considering the work from [71]–[73] the chosen method is a valid approach and delivers usable array performance for the required frequency range. Nordborg et.al. [74] prove the benefit of an irregular spiral array approach which improves performance in the frequency range from 200 Hz to 3.4 kHz, over other simpler array shapes. The irregular array design approach of Sarradj proposes an optimal array design with no numerical optimisation in the position generation.

The given formulas from [70] were applied to the design of straight pipes. Due to transportation limitations in passenger cars and available pipes, a three-arm design with straight pipes of 2 m in lengths was chosen. The cables for signals and power run inside the pipe underneath the PCBs, as shown in Figure 14. The pipes supply the needed structural strength and robustness. Inside the pipe a 3D printed cage holds the processing PCB and cables in place. This construction is set up separately from the pipe and is slid into the pipe for assembly. The resulting design is a spiral spread over the three arms, it is illustrated in Figure 11 by a blue line connecting each microphone in the array. A spiral design has the benefit of non-repeating microphone distances in the array which otherwise can cause spatial aliasing by fitting the same wavelength in multiple pairs of array microphones. This phenomenon is explained with ambiguous signal path distances to one point source in front of the array. Furthermore, the spiral applied to three arms generates a good filtering performance of a wide range of wavelengths, by including small distances and long distances in the structure. The distance of each microphone to the array center follows the rules from [70, p. 6] and the formula:

$$r = R \sqrt{\frac{m}{M}} \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, M \quad (1)$$

Together with the angle ϕ relative to the first array arm pointing up each microphone position is laid out in polar coordinates around the central junction point of the array arms. The tree arm design is generated with the angle ϕ of 120° :

$$\phi = 2\pi \frac{(1 + \sqrt{V})}{2} \quad (2)$$

Where R stands for the array diameter and the number of microphones, M, in the array. In the adapted equation (2), the wanted angle ϕ between two arms in that array is inserted in equation (3) to generate the wanted microphone pattern.

$$V = \left(\frac{\phi}{360} * 2 - 1 \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

The use of 2 m pipes and the required 24 mm length for each microphone unite inside the pipe leads to the 64 microphone channels ($M = 64$) in three arms joined together in a central connection piece. The array position pattern is calculated with calculated arm positions from the values $R = 2$ m and $\phi = 120^\circ$ which were inserted into equation (1) and equation (3). The calculated positions are plotted in Figure 11 with a clear decreasing microphone spacing towards the outer array positions. The distances between two microphone units reduce toward the outer positions down to a minimum distance of 24 mm.

Figure 11: Calculated array microphone positions on three arms with [70]; front view with a minimal distance between two microphones of 24 mm, every circle represents one microphone position, blue spiral for illustration of the decreasing distances towards the arm tips not implemented

Each arm is tilted by 30° in z-direction towards the source position to enhance the rear signal damping. The resulting position pattern is generating a beamforming pattern that is evaluated by the beampattern and the beamwidth at -3 dB from the maximum of the main lobe. The directional characteristics are described by the point spread function (PSF), which is the resulting image with the processed signals of a white noise point source. In the simulation, the noise source is set to a 150 m distance acoustic grid. The central position of the source is visible in every result of the processed PSFs in Figure 12. The simulation results provide information on the behaviour of the designed array structure to noise sources in the wind park scale. The simulation and its outcome are the measures of source separations, although in wind turbine application noise sources are emitted over a larger surface. The shown filtering performance images are processed from the white noise point source with frequency steps from 1 kHz to 9 kHz with a 1 kHz step size.

Figure 12: Beampattern processed at nine different frequencies from 1 kHz to 9 kHz focusing on a white noise point source in the centre of the image plane. Colour scale set to 10 dB SPL dynamic from the image maximum value

The processed graphs in Figure 12 show the three individual array arms generate a repeating pattern with 120° rotational symmetry. The pattern size is decreasing with increasing frequency, up to a ~ 3 dB radius of 0.7 m at 9 kHz, see Table 3 for the whole list. The beamwidth (main lobe width) b , described by [69, p. 43 ff], is frequency and microphone position-dependent and is a measure for the frequency-specific source separation resolution. Lower source frequencies generate wider beam patterns, b , due

to larger signal wavelengths. On a wind turbine scale the beamwidth at 1 kHz of 7.6 m is capable of assigning signals to wind turbine parts. The presented simulation results show that the array is reaching the required 5 m source separation resolution for frequencies above 1000 Hz with the -3 dB radius.

Table 3: Array beam width b simulation results at different frequencies, PSF with acoustic plane 150 m distance to the array

evaluation frequency f_c in Hz	b or position -3 dB from Max in m (resolution 0.1 m)
1000	7.6
2000	3.4
3000	2.2
4000	1.6
5000	1.3
6000	1.1
7000	0.9
8000	0.8
9000	0.7

The simulated performance measures provide information on the acoustic source positioning performance of array design. It shows that eight out of nine frequencies fulfil the 5 m required resolution on the acoustic gird. The 1 kHz resolution violates the 5 m resolution, but the calculation of only one frequency from the signal spectrum is a theoretical measure. In the wind park application of the array chunks of multiple hundred Hertz are processed to increase the signal energy for processing. For the application at a wind turbine is the simulated performance sufficient. It enables detailed investigations on turbine parts on the scale of 120 m height wind turbine. The performance of the manufactured array is presented in Section 4.6.2.

4.4.3 Array structure development

The designed microphone array positions are realised with a structure of 2 m aluminum pipes joint together in a central unit which includes the optical camera. The usage of aluminum pipes built a slim profile array with the required robustness and inner array stiffness to ensure the microphone positions. By the central hub design, an array with fewer openings to seal is realized and cables can be routed

inside the housing. This design approach can also be found in the star 48 arrays of gfai tech [75, p. 48] and is the state of the art for this size arrays that are applied to record acoustic emissions outdoors. The available design of the star 48 does have different microphone positions. The array arms are tilted 30° in the source direction as developed in Section 4.4.2. The described structure is shown in Figure 13. The holes in the array arm provide the sections for the microphones. Each hole is positioned following the design from section 4.4.2.

Figure 13: Partial view of the array structure with central junction piece (orange), array arms (grey), optical camera (yellow), and electronic case (green) in a 3D rendering, showing the final array

One example of this internal pipe structure is shown in Figure 15, where the red pieces are designed to form different distances between the microscope cages and to decouple vibrations. The smaller microphone PCBs are designed to fit into oblong holes that are cut in the aluminium pipes. Each contained PCB is holding state-of-the-art electronic components with their needed connections and this defines the size of the boards. With the holes in the pipes, the inner cage holds the microphone PCB to sit flush with the outer pipe surface as shown in Figure 14. The emerging gap in between the PCB and pipe is filled with a 3D-printed rubber-like material that also covers the PCB with a membrane for protection. The detailed design of this flexible part is described in Chapter 4.4.

Figure 14: Schematic cut view of the equipped pipe design with labels describing each part

The structural pipes are housing the internal structure of an inner cage that is holding the microphones units PCB and the cable connections. The cage also holds damping pieces under each PCB together with damping foam between two microphones for sound isolation and pipe noise elimination. All inner structural pieces except for the foam are 3D-printed and are individually engineered to ensure the correct distances on each array arm. The pipe insides serve two tasks and fulfil different requirements. The first requirement is to find a mountable design, which is watertight after mounting. The inner structure shown in Figure 15 is slid into the pipe fully assembled and the microphones together with their protective membrane are put through the hole after the inner structure is aligned with them. The second requirement is to build high-quality acoustic performance and reduce structural vibrations. The processing PCB and sensor board are vibrationally isolated from the structure by 3D-printed flexible parts under the PCB and around the protective membrane. In addition to the structural vibrations, the air volumes above the processing PCB are capsuled from the pipe volume. All remaining spaces underneath and between the cages are filled with acoustic damping foam MicroPor© [76] for further pressure wave damping and microphone acoustic isolation. The last requirement for the array structure is cable management and simple manufacturing processes. The cables are routed under the PCB inside the cages. Each cable connector is secured by a cable tie for advanced robustness and no cable vibration or movement after assembly. The distance pieces coloured in red in Figure 15 are 3D-printed for every distance and provide the needed stiffness concurrent with minimal additional weight.

Figure 15: Example array structure pipe internal parts assembled in a 3D-rendering. The PCB (green) is held in place by the PCB cage (yellow), microphones carrier under the protective membrane (purple), distances and structural stiffness is generated by distance pieces (red), pipes housing set transparent for detailed visibility

4.4.4 Data communication structure

Array microphones units send the recorded sound data to a central acquisition unit. This central unit collects the 64 microphone channels and converts the microphones channels into one data stream for the connected computer. The computer does the file handling and storage as well as the image acquisition of the connected optical camera. The figure shows the block diagram with signals in an acoustic array with 64 microphones. The microphones are daisy-chained into pairs of two. Each pair is connected via TDM2, see the time diagram of TDM2 in Figure 16, to the central data acquisition unit [77]. TDM is the current state-of-the-art audio transmission protocol for unidirectional audio data. Audio data are streamed in cable lengths up 2.5 m in the array structure, which is made possible by the selected TDM2 with the low BCLK of 3.072 MHz's. Other TDM modes with more bus participants were unable to transmit data error-free in experiments. The central unit was developed by the project partner and provides the needed power for the microphone unit or Multi-Sensor Microphone (MSM) together with

clock signals of the TDM connection. The MSM reacts as a single microphone and sends data dependent on the Serial-Data-Word Select Clock. This way each unit in the array is synchronized and sends data with 48 kHz Sampling rate.

Figure: Array sound signal data communication structure, data, and clock for communication

The data transfer and synchronization between the MSM and the central unit is adaptable to application needs. The number of units per data transfer line SDATA is scalable together with the number of bits per transfer slot with a limit of 32 bits. The more units are transmitting to the TDMx data line the higher the BCLK when the LRCLK rate is kept the same. So, the maximum cable length gets reduced with the higher clock rates. In the wind park array, TDM2 is used to transfer the microphone data over up to 2.5 m long cables inside the array arms. The usage of the TDM protocol for the audio data enables future applications of the microphone units with different configurations and hardware components.

Figure 16: TDM2 schematic data transfer from [78, p. 12]

The received microphone data are collected in parallel inside the central unit and are transmitted via the serial USB connection to the attached PC. The PC holds the data storage and transmits files over an ethernet network. These connections were not developed in the project.

4.4.5 Multi-Sensor Microphone

The Multi-Sensor Microphone was specifically developed to meet the mechanical requirements of the pipe design and the acoustic and electrical requirements for an array application.

The MSM PCB design is described by [79, Ch. 8]. The author adapted the developed solutions described in Chapter 4.3.1 to the array pipe design and evaluated the newly developed hardware. The key novelty for the wind park array is the detachable microphone PCB and the required connectors to allow the mounting. Further the board integrated voltage converter allow a robust power supply in the array arms. An occurring voltage drop from the 5 V power supply due to long cable ways does not affect the required processor specific 3.3 V supply. The manufactured MSM units are presented in Figure 17. In addition, the power supply section and the reset behaviour were improved over the previous designs to ensure controlled unit resets when needed. The block diagram with the contained components is attached in Appendix A: Multi-Sensor-Microphone block diagram.

Figure 17: Manufactured four-layer MSM PCB, a) top view with attached MEMS microphone PCB and b) bottom view with processor and voltage control ICs visible

The microphone units boot after the power is delivered by the central unit and start the synchronized data transmission after a successful self-test. In the sensor unit, the microphones are soldered to a detached PCB. With this design decision, the sensor PCB is connected to the main PCB after the inner pipe structure is inserted into the pipe. The sensors sit flush with the outer pipe surface to improve the acoustic behaviour and enable potentially needed protection. The SPH0641LU4H [64] and MP34DT05 [80, p. 05] are the microphones used in this design. There is also an integrated power voltage supervision to ensure a power-on-reset after a power loss. The connectors between the daisy-chained sensor units and the central unit are using the Milli-Grid Connector System [81] to transport power and signals over one cable connection. Figure 18 shows assembled units with finished cabling. The detached microphone PCB with the oblong shape is visible in that Figure. This part is attached to the main PCB after the inner part with all microphones for one arm is slid into the aluminium.

Figure 18: Array structure with assembled cabling and attached microphone board, black plastic cage structure with dividing walls between the microphones, a) side view with elastic damping element underneath the processing board, b) top view with all connectors visible

The used microprocessor does not support the used TDM interface connection natively. To be able to transmit the recorded data to the central unit the controller needs an adaptation to its serial interface. The included timer-counter module is configured to generate the needed synchronisation signals by counting the right amount of clock edges after the LRCLK falling edge. With this approach, every microphone can be programmed to transmit its data-words after the programmed number of clock edges and the array can work with different TDM types.

4.5 Microphone protective membrane development

The microphone protection needed for a continuous outdoor application was developed for the described wind park usage. The mechanical design with a protective element above the microphones is shown in Figure 19. Here the oblong holes in the aluminium pipe are covered with the protective membrane. These protections are specifically designed for the wind park applications frequency range. Frequency response with a flat curve in the applications spectrum from 20 Hz to 9 kHz is the design goal.

Figure 19: Protective membrane design from Wenzel and Rettig (Wenzel and Rettig, 2021, fig. 2)

In the development process, unique design ideas were developed, printed in a 3D-printer, and measured. The final design together with the design process was published in *Applied Acoustics* [1], it was developed from multiple initial design ideas. Designs with a flat and thin membrane above the whole sensor PCB, rectangular-shaped membrane sections, and other designs were evaluated. During the development investigations on the shapes and dimensions with over 300 samples printed and tested resulted in a dedicated acoustic membrane above the microphones sound port resulting in a small circular-shaped membrane section. The whole protective membrane was 3D printed from a flexible TPU material [82] with a thickness of 0.5 mm to act as the main transducing sound port, see Figure 20. There are two images provided the Figure 20 a) showing a rendered image with the protective membrane inserted and the circular membrane section visible in the left part above the microphone. The second, Figure 20 b), shows the membrane sample mounted into a pipe section. Analysis shows that incoming sound pressure waves hit the membrane, force it to vibrate, and result in pressure changes measured by the microphones inside the closed cavity underneath the membrane. This transducer principle is the reason for investigations on the vibrational behaviour were made and resonance frequencies were investigated.

Figure 20: Applied membrane in a pipe assembly with PCBs inside the pipe, a) rendering out and b) manufactured sample with pipe section; both show the dedicated membrane above the microphones sound ports

The design process was supported by vibrational simulations with investigations on resonance frequencies. It was processed with an FEM simulation tool to identify vibrational modes and unwanted parts with high vibrational amplitude. One example of a vibration simulation is shown in Figure 21. It shows the vibrations response of the first mode with an incoming sound wave frequency of 760 Hz in Figure 21 a). Figure 21 b) is showing the vibrational response with three peaks of amplitudes formed by the third vibrational mode. Simulated vibrational mode positions were used to focus the vibration on membrane parts that interact with the microphones. Changes in thickness, shape and size were used in this project. The Simulated membranes were printed and measured in an anechoic chamber to compare the simulated and measured behaviour. For this purpose, the printed membranes attached to the microphone were placed in the anechoic chamber together with an analogue reference microphone and a sound source. The measured reference signal was used to For a detailed description of the measurement procedure please compare the published results in [1]. In addition to the mentioned development process did the material model development play a role in understanding the vibrational behaviour and the shape influences. The aim for the material model in the simulation was to reproduce the vibrations measured

with a printed membrane that is manufactured in layers. This was achieved by adapted material parameters.

Figure 21: Simulation results of a flat protective membrane design; vibration analysis at mode frequencies a) @760 Hz first vibrational mode and b) @1000 Hz third vibrational mode

The membrane development process was enabled by the combination of design, simulation, manufacturing, and measurements. Each step's results were compared, and design changes were based on findings from previous iterations. The result is a membrane that is tailored for the wind park application with the needed parameters and protection.

4.6 System characterisation

The developed system characterisation was undertaken in two steps. Firstly, the individual microphones were measured in an acoustic lab. Later the equipped array was set up for characterisation measurements with 64 microphone channels.

The investigation was used to prove the correct functionality of every component on the microphone unit and to evaluate the unit's capabilities. Array measurements were challenged in their spatial filtering capabilities and against the simulation and design considerations.

4.6.1 Single-channel characterisation

Evaluation measurements for the microphone characteristics were performed in a one microphone setup. These measurements were made in an acoustic chamber to achieve reproducible conditions in temperature and room acoustics.

The measurement setup for the microphones tested was deducted from the Standard [83]. It describes calibration and characterization methods for standard ½ inch microphones. MEMS microphones used in the application are not covered by the standard, though the basic method was adapted. As described in the standard, a reference microphone [84] was placed 1 mm in front of the MEMS microphones sound port. This arrangement was placed 1m in front of the sound source. The frequency sweep from 50 Hz to 15 kHz within 30 seconds sound pressure reaches simultaneously. Detailed images and descriptions of the setup and its usage are provided in [1, Ch. 2.4.1]. For these investigations, only the microphone for audible frequencies MP34DT05 from STMicroelectronics [80, p. 05] was part of the measurements. The resulting frequency responses of the single microphone are evaluated against the channel 0 microphone of the array. This approach shows the deviation between the different microphones, see Figure 22, which stays within the ± 1 dB SPL range for the application relevant Frequencies up to 9 kHz. During the measurements, the anechoic chamber temperature was 21.1° C with 41% RH.

Figure 22: MEMS microphone frequency response in comparison to microphone 0

The tested sample microphone provided frequency responses in the required frequency range. The evaluation showed the suitability of this approach of each microphone, which is needed for the array calibration for every microphone. The tests showed the units fulfil the acoustic requirements for the array to be used in the wind park application.

4.6.2 Array characterisation

Array acoustic behaviour was evaluated in a reverberation room together with the spatial filtering capabilities in an anechoic chamber. Results from the anechoic chamber are compared with the simulated beamforming patterns to prove the array design and the correct microphone positions in the array.

In the first investigation, the homogeneity of the array's microphones without applied corrections and calibration was evaluated. This is measured in a reverberation room with an equally white noise exiting the sound field. This ensures with a white noise sound source the same sound pressure distribution at

every sensor in the array over time. All measured channels were subtracted by the frequency response of channel 0 as reference. All channels deviation from channel 0 stay within a corridor of ± 2 dB up to 15 kHz as displayed in Figure 23.

Figure 23: Array white noise recording in a reverberation room of 64 microphone channels with lines at ± 3 dB SPL, reference: recorded frequency response of array channel 0

The beamforming measurement results in Figure 24 shows a time-domain-beamformer when provided with a source frequency of 1000 Hz sine wave with a main beamwidth $b = 230$ mm at an image plane 4 m away from the array. This measurement was performed in an anechoic room with a small sound source. This result is compared to the source separation simulation performed in Section 4.4.2. The aim is to validate the simulations results and test if the measurement results fulfil the requirements at wind park distances. Scaling to the wind park dimensions of the measurement setup was made for comparison of the lab measurements and the simulations. The measured result projection to the wind park scale with distance, $d = 150$ m, results in a beamwidth of 8.625 m at a wind turbine. A comparison to the results of the simulations in Table 3 ($f_c = 1$ kHz and $b = 7.6$ m) shows the difference of 1 m with an experimental not ideal sound source with a speaker membrane diameter of 60 mm. Both array investigation proves

the wind park-ready performance of the developed array hardware. Although, the required 5 m spatial filtering separation is not reached in the frequency range up to 1.5 kHz signal frequency. A source signal localisation will be possible due to the large scale of the wind turbines.

Figure 24: Array beamforming pattern of a noise source with bandwidth from 300 Hz to 1.5 kHz at 4 m distance to the array in the measurement setup in an anechoic chamber

The measurements showed that the designed array can perform effective spatial filtering in laboratory environments. Further, will the application and field measurements show how signal processing and the results will perform.

4.7 Experimental field setup

4.7.1 Array wind park positioning

The recording position for the array in the wind park should be chosen with different boundary conditions considered for wind turbine signatures recording and to optimise the use of the facilities, like

wind sensors and temperature sensors, present in the wind park. The chosen positions should fulfil the requirements of the standard IEC 61400-11 [10] related to the array's position relative to the wind turbine and wind sensors. In addition to the standard's requirements, the position should provide good protection against agricultural machines or other interferences e.g., animals. It should also be positioned at a suitable distance from the wind turbine to ensure focus on the whole turbine and within a radius of the turbine to record evaluable signals.

Noise emissions recorded in a wind park are a combination of wind turbine noise levels and the background noises emitted by surrounding other sources. The theoretical distance dependency of the noise level of a typical Enercon wind turbine 1.5 m above ground simulated by [85, Fig. 1] is presented in Figure 25. The recordable noise strongly depends on the distance to the tower. The estimates may lead to a usable distance from a wind turbine at a maximum distance of 300 m to achieve noise levels of more than 40 dB(A) in dry weather conditions.

Figure 25: Theoretical estimated distance noise level dependency [85]

The available infrastructure, like grid power, wired network connection, and auxiliary environmental sensors, should be useful. The roof of the equipment container at the yellow mark in Figure 26 a) fulfilled all imposed requirements and was chosen for the measurement campaigns with the orange highlighted wind turbine in focus at 145 m distance to the tower. This position covers the requirements developed in the project together with the requirements from the IEC 61400-11 [10]. Figure 26 b) shows an image of the microphone array pointing at the wind turbine and recording noise emissions.

Figure 26: Experimental setup in the Wind Park a) Wind Park map with array position (yellow rectangle) and auxiliary positions (red rectangle), orange marked wind turbine of interest; b) picture of the manufactured microphone array pointing at the wind turbine, it is placed on top of a shipping container for protection

At the measurement site, the data was recorded in time frames of 30 seconds chunks with a time gap of 20 seconds to the next recording. The reason for that is the used software Noiseimage [86] that is bundled with the central unit. The benefit of that behaviour is that audio data of all channels are combined in one single file together with the camera data and information about the array and the array microphone positions.

4.7.2 Acoustic application of the array in the wind park

The developed array is applied in the wind park where the array orientation and height above the ground is fixed. For an effective beamforming computation, the mapping grid in the wind park application of an acoustic image plane is defined with 1 m grid resolution. The acoustic grid is defined to cover the turbine part of interest at a distance of 145 m away from the array position to the tower base. These parts include the nacelle and the blade's sweeping area. For illustration, Figure 27 shows the array

arrangement with the wind turbine together with the grid (arbitrary grid for better illustration) and its axes. The distance error at the nacelle height due to the measured distance from the microphone array to the tower's base is acceptable since the pressure waves travel through the projected image plane with negligible position error.

Figure 27: Geometric description of the algorithmic arrangement of the microphone array and the wind turbine for the beamforming algorithms at a wind turbine (arbitrary grid for better illustration)

The orientation and the tilt of the microphone array tilt towards the turbine's nacelle are visible in Figure 28. It is shown that the optical camera's field of view includes the rotor sweep area.

Figure 28: Operating wind turbine, image recorded with array integrated camera showing the array orientation and image plane centre underneath the nacelle

The acoustic grid position is adapted with the optical reference from multiple reference images like the one in Figure 28. Central rotor hub and nacelle position is $x = 3$ m and $y = 18.5$ m from the image centre. This results in a maximal circle of rotors sweep area centrum with the mentioned coordinates and a diameter of 58.5 m.

The data recording was performed in two periods. The first recording was made from the 5th of December 2019 to the 15th of December 2019 followed by the second from the 11th of May 2020 to the 4th of July 2020. During these two periods, 76 hours of quasi-continuous acoustical array data were collected.

4.7.3 Auxiliary data

There were two auxiliary environmental data sensors installed in the wind park. The first is a LIDAR WINDCUBE® v2 [87] recording the wind speed and directions at different heights from the ground. The second sensor array is mounted on a wind mast in the wind park and consists of different sensors at different heights. The last wind park data source is the wind turbine with operational data available during the array recording. The circumstances of the data availability during the two data collection campaigns are provided the Figure 29. Here the gap in sensor data availability is shown and analysis has to take that into account.

Figure 29: Auxiliary data availability during measurement campaigns overview

Figure 29 shows an overview of the data collection and the sensor data available at that time. There were two data collection campaigns in two seasons of the year and weather conditions to prove the array capability and record different wind turbine conditions.

4.8 Conclusion

This Chapter developed the array of hardware based on the requirements compiled in previous Chapters. The developed hardware was evaluated as suitable for the described wind park application. Test and measurements showed that the acoustical performance and the spatial filtering capabilities fulfil the requirements. In the last Section, the wind park application with considerations relating to distance and auxiliary equipment availability was described. The applied array hardware together with the auxiliary sensors data is used in analysis and investigations on wind turbine acoustic emissions.

Chapter 5 Use cases and Applications

5.1 Introduction

Chapter 5 uses the array hardware developed in previous Chapters and uses recorded acoustic wind park data for two applications. The first application is using the ability to continuously measure the operation of the array and analyse the recorded data according to the current standard of noise measurement at wind turbine. With this, it is possible to overcome the need for manual equipment operation in a wind park. The second data application uses the spatial filtering application of the acoustic array and described the development of automated focusing on wind turbine parts. This could enable future analysis on parts of the wind turbine in monitoring applications.

5.2 Continuous wind turbine noise monitoring

5.2.1 Introduction

Prediction and simulations of noise emitted by wind turbines are made during wind park planning and after turbine deployment. Forecasts of emitted noise levels during operation are based on detailed information about noise and signatures recorded at operating wind turbines of the same kind. A satisfactory level of detail of noise emissions data coverage in a wide range of wind and environmental conditions is necessary to improve the current procedure of single dedicated noise investigations that are conducted in certain conditions. Measured data from the wind park include wind field data as well

as information on noise sources position for propagation models to fully describe the turbine behaviour. The current standards for noise measurements at wind turbines, IEC 61400-11 [10], define the parameters of data collections and the measurement equipment. In certain wind parks, the conditions of the required wind speeds and directions are only present for short periods in a year. This leads to issues in planning and homologation of newly constructed wind parks. A new approach with strategically placed equipment recording emitted noise continuously could be used to overcome the requirements to conduct measurements at various positions in the wind park by being installed at a single position and left to take measurements over several days in the wind park. This approach addresses the current gap of single measurements performed in different positions in dedicated periods and presents an approach of continuous recordings from one position. This covers the required conditions and noise level measurements without any manual intervention.

The research question for this section is:

How can a continuous array measurement be used to meet the requirements of the IEC 61400-11 standard which stipulates temporally measurements using a single microphone at various positions around the wind turbine?

The approach achieves comparable results with continuous measurements in wind parks by recording noise emissions for extended periods of time instead of conducting discrete measurements with suitable wind conditions is discussed in the section. For recordings from a fixed position in the wind park, not all operational directions will be represented in the same way.

5.2.2 Applications of loudness measurements in wind parks

Loudness measurements in wind parks are typically performed with a single-channel audio analyser with analogue microphones as described by Katinas et al. [85]. The analysis made with this kind of equipment does benefit from the standardised signal processing methods and the well-established procedures of sound report creation. Different spectra and octave bands spectra, tonality analysis, and

simple continuous weighted sound pressure levels are methods applied to recording in wind parks to understand the acoustic wind turbine behaviour.

The use of a single-channel acoustic device requires measurements to be conducted at different distances to the wind turbine to create sound propagation profiles in different wind conditions [41]. This approach benefits from the use of simple recording equipment and standardised analysis techniques. Although the recording is sampling the sound field at one position, sound sources can be assigned to one wind turbine by level differences. For better spatial sampling ability, an acoustic array must be deployed.

5.2.3 EN IEC 61400-11 Wind turbine measurement standard

The international standard IEC 61400-11 [10] dictates the approach for noise level recordings for the wind energy sector and also facilitates comparable measurement results at wind turbines. Its current version IEC 61400-11 is focused on noise recordings from wind turbine manufacturers, operators, and planners for measurement guidance of complex acoustic emissions from wind turbines. It defines the equipment requirements, auxiliary sensors, and positions relative to the wind turbine. Measurement results should be considered for noise load investigations and compliance with emission requirements.

The application of the standard to the developed array measurements is made to compare the continuous recording approach against dedicated recordings. Dedicated recordings are performed to comply with the standards e.g., acoustical performance verification of a wind turbine. The continuous recording is performed with no direct purpose but might also cover the required parameters for acoustic noise recordings.

To use the standard at the wind turbine type Nordex N117/3000 Delta [57], where measurements have been conducted in this research, the required distances and wind direction angular regions have to be calculated. To comply with the standard the maximum distance between the microphone array and the base of the tower, R_0 , is calculated from the nacelle height H and the rotor diameter D using equation (4).

$$R_0 = H + \frac{D}{2} = 120 \text{ m} + \frac{116.8 \text{ m}}{2} = 178.4 \text{ m} \quad (4)$$

The setup used in this research had a distance of 145 m between the microphone array and the base of the turbine. This is outside the permissible tolerance of ± 30 m and the results presented should be considered in this context. Turbine orientation translates into 208° for upwind conditions and 28° for downwind conditions from recordings. There are two measurement positions in downwind $\pm 60^\circ$ from the centre line, which translates to 328° and 88° for these positions. The plan of the four mentioned measurement positions is presented in Figure 30.

Figure 30: Pattern of microphone positions at the wind turbine relative to the wind direction from IEC 61400-11 [10, p. 12]

The standard describes a single microphone setup on a flat acoustically hard surface on the ground. It also requires a class 1 microphone which is shielded by a large foam windshield that must be calibrated before and after every recording. The array is made of digital MEMS microphones and is not covered by a windshield. The array structure including the protective membranes provides shielding against direct wind influences at the microphone membrane, but the results presented should be considered in this context.

5.2.4 Continuous noise load measurement

The development of a method of continuous monitoring in a wind park is based on the idea of a recording device that stays in one position for the whole duration of the measurement campaign. With this approach, there is no measurement position change and operator action required. The correct placement of the recording device is crucial. The setup should fulfil distance requirements, the relative positions of angular regions and must collect acoustic data in the needed wind conditions.

Therefore, the main wind direction in the wind park plays a significant role since most data will be collected in this angular region. The main wind directions at the test site are south-west and west-south-west, as shown in Figure 26, which was translated into the heading of 208° towards the wind turbine at the recording position.

Taking the measured data and applying the positions in accordance with the requirements of IEC 61400-11 results in the plot shown in Figure 31. The fixed array position translates into four allowed wind turbine orientation ranges upwind, downwind and $\pm 60^\circ$ from the upwind position.

Figure 31 shows the datapoint measured within the allowed 30° of error of the four positions. The main positions 1 (cyan stars) with 450 data points and secondary position 3 (red square) with 1000 data points provide the most data. The measured wind speeds were up to 11 m/s (39.6 km/h). The alternative positions are shown 2 (blue triangles) with 148 data points and 4 with zero data points.

Figure 31: Wind speed measured at the wind turbine nacelle plotted over the azimuth angles; marked areas corresponding to the allowed angular ranges by the IEC 61400-11 [34]

In addition, the wind speed distribution in Figure 32 shows that the wind turbine power output is the same. It shows that the majority of data points are under 1200 kW which can be explained by the relatively low wind speed during the recordings.

Figure 32: Wind turbine power output in kW plotted over the azimuth angles; marked areas corresponding to the allowed angular ranges by the IEC 61400-11 [10]

The standards limit wind speeds as follows: “The wind speed range for documentation is related to the specific wind turbine. As a minimum it is defined as the hub height wind speed from 0.8 to 1.3 times the wind speed at 85 % of maximum power rounded to bin centres” [10, p. 6]. For the measured wind turbine, these limits are $0.8 * 9.6 \text{ m/s} = 7.68 \text{ m/s}$ and $1.3 * 9.6 \text{ m/s} = 12.48 \text{ m/s}$. Applying these limits to the data in position 1 than 9.1% of the data points are within the limits and in position 3 19.1% of all data points are within the limits.

5.2.5 Results

The acoustic analysis applied on the recordings made with the developed microphone array is presented in the section.

Analysis of the sound pressure level weighted with the dBA-weighting filter shows different patterns depending on the parameter in relation.

Figure 33: Sound pressure level comparison from 10 minutes averages in two different angular ranges, left graphs showing range 1 for downwind conditions and right graphs showing angular range 3 for upwind conditions; comparing wind turbine power output to dBA SPL and the wind speed measured at a wind mast to dBA SPL; fitted linear curves with extrapolation to 3100 kW or 12.6 m/s the maximum ratings for the turbine type due to IEC 61400-11 [48]

The noise level measured by the central MEMS microphone in the array compared to the wind turbine power output and the predominant wind speed at the recording time is discussed. Looking at Figure 33, the left side graphs show recorded data point from the upwind position 1 and the right side shows the

data from the downwind positions 3. The trend in all four graphs is that with higher wind speeds, the overall sound pressure level increases. This trend is more prevalent in the two lower graphs since there is more coupling of the wind speed to the recorded SPLs. The transformed wind turbine power shows a greater impact on the noise levels in the downwind constellation. These are the reference positions from the IEC 61400-11 [10]. The corresponding fitted graphs plotted in Figure 33 are presented in Table 4. The discussed wind speed and turbine power dependencies of the noise levels can also be found in the equation parameters. The gradient of power is ten time higher between position 1 and 2. During the measurement campaign, only a small portion of the wind speeds occurred above 7 m/s, which is below the 12 m/s needed for the maximum power output.

Table 4: Equations of the linear fit in Figure 33

Range	Equation of the linear fit
(1) Power	$y = 0.0034 * WTPW \text{ in } W + 43 \text{ dBA SPL}$
(1) Wind speed	$y = 1.22241 * AuxWS \text{ in } \frac{m}{s} + 39 \text{ dBA SPL}$
(2) Power	$y = 0.00032 * WTPW \text{ in } W + 43 \text{ dBA SPL}$
(2) Wind speed	$y = -0,10657 * AuxWS \text{ in } \frac{m}{s} + 44 \text{ dBA SPL}$

5.2.6 Discussions

The wind turbine noise emission monitoring approach of continuous recording of noise levels from one position has been discussed in this section. Results show that although the field measurements were made in two different seasons and over multiple weeks, not all required operational conditions were measured. High wind speed conditions with high power outputs are required by the current standard those were not covered by the shown recordings. This shows that a long-term data recording is needed, and it should cover multiple months to cover the required conditions of stronger winds.

Figure 33 shows that data measured in the angular range 1 show the expected dependency of an increased sound pressure level by increased turbine power or wind speed. The angular range 3 does not provide this clear dependency in the measured data, although noise is measured in this range. Further analysis could achieve a clearer dependency of wind turbine noise emission related to their orientation to the position of measurement. More data points are needed in the other orientations to do this analysis.

The analysis has shown that the selection of one-channel parameters from the array's multichannel data can be used to understand noise emission. However, the microphones array is not calibrated to fulfil the standards from IEC 61400-11. The selected values could not be used for noise reports, which makes an additional calibrated analogue microphone within the array setup necessary. The additional microphone could add additional low-frequency performance, although it may need more protection than provided by a foam windshield. During field deployment, protection against environmental influences is crucial.

The combination of an analogue reference microphone and an acoustic array would be beneficial for long-term measurement campaigns. Both devices bring added value to the existing approaches. But additional development is needed to apply the reference microphone in a suitable outdoor housing. Furthermore, the auxiliary data availability must be increased from the current 0.1 Hz of this investigation to 1 Hz or more to allow a more detailed analysis to be conducted.

5.3 Wind turbine blade noise source separation

5.3.1 Introduction

The information on sound source positions can be used for a more detailed acoustic analysis of wind turbines than a single channel recording without any directional information. The advantage of the developed microphone array for wind turbine investigations is the ability of the spatial sound field recording to achieve spatial directivity. Spatial sound separation uses beamforming techniques on acoustic grid positions for noise source differentiation. The discrete grid positions are scanned and the whole grid is further analysed or plotted. Although the grid consists of discrete positions, each processed point signal is the result of the directivity pattern, which were simulated and measured in Section 4.5.2. The resulting images include side lobes that influence the signal power of other points.

Acoustic investigations of the whole turbine structure or turbine parts can generate a general picture of the system's condition and the surrounding noise sources. The turbine orientation influences the noise levels in the recording for a fixed recording position. Different noise emission patterns and the changing orientation with different noise positions make noise source position processing necessary. In addition, the source focusing can overcome that ambient noise can mask the turbine emissions levels by overshooting levels of the source of interest.

The target of this development is a spatial filtering procedure that overcomes these limitations in most conditions by assigning a signal to a position on the acoustic map and with that to a turbine component. With that approach, the procedure will keep track of one turbine component and outputs the component's sound signature in various weather and wind conditions. For this development, the turbine blades were chosen as the part to track for the algorithm. Wind turbine blades and in particular their surface area is not monitorable by other sensors in a wind turbine and the newly developed approach would close this gap. A typical problem causing blade surface defects is bird strikes damaging the surface of the blades[88], [89]. The processed output signal would include whistle noises from a surface defect and would enable further analysis due to position information that includes which of the three blades and

where on the blade a defect is located. The Precisely determined blade positions are crucial for the resulting focusing performance of the source separation, a position detection in a 5 m x 5 m area is required.

This section describes the development of automated spatial sound source separation in a wind park and applies these to the array audio recording from a wind park. Therefore, the wind park array sound recordings are processed using beamforming algorithms.

The objective of the investigation of beamforming for spatial filtering of wind turbine noise is to answer the question of how spatial filtering can be applied in a wind park scenario for continuous acoustic monitoring. To answer this question, the hardware used to conduct the measurements and the signal processing algorithms applied to the turbines noise emissions are presented. It addresses a practical implementation of an acoustic grid at operating wind turbines, a beamforming approach, and a source selection of interest.

5.3.2 State of the art wind turbine sound separation

Processing spatial filtering in the wind turbine applications follows the approach of an acoustic grid in the turbine blade plane as the presented grid in Figure 27. The processing of the acoustic signals into an acoustical map is done by the frequency domain beamforming. Frequency domain beamforming is based on the time domain approach of the delay-and-sum beamforming algorithm. Both approaches use a spatially recorded sound field and the resulting time difference of arrival (TDOA) at each array microphone [69, p. 39 ff]. The TDOA and knowledge of the array geometry are used to synchronise the recorded signals for one grid position with one directivity pattern. This is the first signal processing step. The microphone signals are delayed by a value corresponding the TDOA of one grid position. In the second step, the delayed signals are added up resulting in the beamformer output signal. Frequency domain algorithms take the same procedure, but the delay is translated into a phase shift. Additional explanations are provided in Section 4.2.

By applying an acoustic image plane in the rotor plane, the analysis shows the integrated noise sources of the three blades moving in circular patterns. In addition, nacelle noise emissions can be found in the rotor plane and are part of the analysis.

Conventional beamforming in the frequency domain has been used by Bale and Johnson [58] at rotational sources in a scale rotor application. Their array which contains 32 microphone channels was calibrated and tested with different noise sources in different wind situations. Their measurements at the wind turbine (600W) test site showed that the used wind turbine has the highest noise emissions from 3 to 10 kHz.

Eric J. Simley [59] describes an array development as well as an application of CLEAN-SC[90], based on the work of [91], beamforming applied for inboard sources at 500 Hz but with higher computational effort compared to conventional beamforming approaches.

Oerlemans and López [14] used a conventional Delay and Sum beamforming approach in a wind tunnel arrangement with a static rotor plane. The algorithm used provides decent noise source distribution on the rotor.

Conventional frequency-domain implementation was used by Buck et al. [27] for a wind turbine array application. The beamforming algorithm was implemented in Matlab over 6-second sections of data with nulled diagonal elements in the cross-spectral matrix for self-noise reduction.

Conventional beamforming was implemented by Oerlemans et al. [53] at a full wind turbine scale to determine the noise sources at the blades for noise reduction measures. The turbine blade surfaces and edges were treated by different measures and were separated in the beamforming processing for analysis.

Conventional Delay and Sum beamforming was used by Zhang et al. [92] in a spherical array for rotational source in a wind tunnel application. A Delay and Sum beamforming algorithm and Classical frequency domain beamforming algorithm have been used by Patel et al. [14] in a scale setup with a full drive train. In addition, they use the deconvolution approach for the mapping of acoustic sources

algorithm [93] and “CLEAN” beamforming procedure first introduced by [91] for deeper analysis after the general overview. The applied algorithms improved the spatial separation.

Multiple steps of beamforming are proposed by S. Oerlemans [11]. Classical beamforming in the frequency domain with a cross-spectral matrix has been used and to improve resolution the main diagonal of the cross-spectral matrix was set to zero.

The wide use of conventional frequency-domain beamforming in wind turbine applications made it the chosen algorithm for source separation in this research.

5.3.3 Algorithm implementation and processing chain

Noise source separation is possible by focusing the acoustic beamformer algorithm onto an area or a point of interest in the acoustic grid. The task for this implementation is the identification of where to focus on the source of interest in the grid plane. There is the challenge of focusing because the turbine is moving and is changing its orientations in different wind conditions. Further to the controlled rotations at the turbine, there is a wind field affecting the sound propagation from the source to the array.

Blades are found to be part of a turbine with a substantial impact on the turbine noise emission (see Section 2.1.3). Any accurate approach that could be used to monitor the blades during operation can help to detect surface defects early. This would help to implement preventive maintenance with the signal output of this approach and can be applied to minimising downtime and extending the lifetime of wind turbines. The key to the effective implementation of the algorithm is the correct identification of the blades' positions and the sound emitted by the blades during operation in changing wind conditions.

The focused approach processes an acoustic map and takes the relevant section for the blades. The blades appear with the highest amplitude in the quadrant before the downwards movement hits the tower, compare [12], [27], [28], [53]. The general noise generated by the blades when moving through the air is the same on the whole rotation, but the downwards movement quadrant produces the highest noise level recorded by the array.

Alloza et al. [55] have described different scenarios and orientations of a wind turbine during array measurements. In each orientation and distance, a different noise source is present within the same frequency range. E.g., the 1/3 octave band at 400 Hz localises a source at the nacelle in one scenario and on the tower base in another scenario.

The blade signal processing is implemented with multiple signal processing steps. Developed Python scripts are attached in Appendix B. The aim is to find the acoustic blade signals in the changing wind conditions. The wind field influences the turbine's parameters by the implemented controller inside the turbine. Further the wind field changes the sound propagation towards the recording array.

Figure 34 illustrates the processing steps of the recorded signals (emissions). The sound field is recorded using the developed microphone array in front of the wind turbine. It records the noise emissions from the blades and wind turbine surroundings. The frequency range selection is one key element of the processing. It is crucial to choose a blade-specific range that is present and not emitted by other parts. The second row of Figure 34 shows the grid adaptation which also helps to focus on the relevant part of the acoustic image plane. Therefore, the orientation data from the wind turbine is processed to the grid which covers the whole area that the blades swept over in their downward movements.

Figure 34: Algorithm approach for blade signal spatial filtering

The pre-processed signals and grid information are fed into a frequency-domain beamformer provided by Acoular [94], a Python-based beamforming and spatial filtering library. The resulting acoustic image

is evaluated for its maximum and the position of the maximum in the adapted grid. In the last processing step, the position of the maximum is reused by a time-based beamformer without prior frequency filtering to provide a broadband time signal of the determined position in the acoustic grid. The time signals contain only information about the blades due to the applied spatial filtering and can be a part of further analysis.

Figure 35: Acoustic grid adaptation scheme which is dependent on the wind turbine orientation (azimuth angle) in absolute angle α_1 , x_1 is adapted to grid the y component is fix

The drawing of the angle dependency of acoustic grid plane shown in Figure 35 illustrates the relationship between the turbine orientation (azimuth angle) α_1 and the projected distance x_1 of the blade area in the image plane. During the development, it was found that the adaptation of the acoustic grid to the distance x_1 provided more reliable results in the found positions, but on the other hand left room for the needed tolerance of the grid size to adapt e.g., for wind drift. The tolerance around the distance x_1 was set to 25 m in both directions in the acoustic grid. Besides the wind turbine operational data depending on grid adaptation there is the second path inserting the acoustic data into the algorithm. It was found that it is needed to select a source-specific frequency range to be able to process its position on a grid. For this process, the source frequencies and typical frequencies of surrounding sources are

considered. The moving blade in the air generates a broadband noise source, although the chosen filtering frequency is present above the surrounding noise floor. The 1/3 Octave band with the central frequency of 4000 Hz provided the clearest positions in manual result evaluations. This frequency range between 3563.6 Hz and 4489.8 Hz allows the determination of the source of the noise with higher accuracies in multiple environmental conditions. The combination of the frequency range selection and the grid adaptation is implemented to ensure a correct focus on the possible blade area with room for wind and other influences to affect the acoustic source position in the acoustic array.

Figure 36: Beamforming example on a field measured during the second measurement campaign in summer 2020; the upper graph shows the selected 4 kHz 1/3 octave band frequency range in the spectrum; blade noise is viable at the lower bypass; the movement of the blades is coming out of the image; measured values: Azimuth angle 125° and Windspeed 4.46 m/s

The acoustic spatial filtering results in Figure 36 and Figure 37 show previously described frequency selection and the resulting acoustic images as an overlay over the optical image. The two different turbine orientations generate different noise positions in the acoustic image. Figure 36 shows the noise sources in the section around the tower. The source on the right is coming straight from the blade and the sources on the left are pressure enhancements from a combination of the blade and the tower. The source on the right is more interesting since it is free from tower interference. Figure 37 shows a

beamforming result from the same data with a different orientation. The two visible sources show that it is necessary to provide a pre-selected grid and apply it only to the relevant area of the acoustic grid.

Figure 37: Beamforming example on a field measured during the second measurement campaign in summer 2020; the upper graph shows the selected 4 kHz frequency range in the spectrum; Blade noise is visible from the blade movement towards the array; measured values: Azimuth angle 185° and Windspeed 4.47 m/s

5.3.4 Results from the application on wind turbine measurements

The application of the described algorithm to the measured wind park data was performed using Python and the Acoular [94] beamforming library. Therefore, wind turbine orientation (red markers) and wind direction (purple marker) measured by a wind mast are plotted on one axis. All data plotted are sorted by increasing wind direction angle. This eliminates the relation to time in the measured data. Not all wind turbine orientations were captured during the measurement campaigns as this correlates with the main wind directions in the wind park, see Figure 26. The outer x-dimension of the swept blade area, the blade tip position when it is horizontal (blue markers) are plotted on the same axis as the resulting x position of the processed maximum (turquoise markers). The minimal and maximal blade tip positions are reached when the turbine swept area is orthogonal to the microphone array's line of sight. Since this

occurs at an azimuth angle of 208° and 28° , see Figure 38, the resulting positions are at ± 58.75 m. The Python script for the result processing is provided in Appendix B: Adaptive spatial filtering analysis script. In that script the data load is performed first, followed by the acoustic data processing and the storage of the results.

Figure 38: Turbine blade maximum x position in relation to the array

The plots in Figure 39 show the results of the grid adaptation to the wind turbine orientation and the processed position of the blades. The algorithmic approach shows the best results in the range from 160° to 240° of the wind turbine orientation. In this region, the red line is showing the data projected on the right azimuth axis. The blade position is plotted in blue from the turbine data followed by the cyan data that were processed with the acoustic approach. The source positions found are located between the outer blade tip and the tower, in the range where they are expected and found in manual analysis. The estimated positions of the maximum on the x-axis are distributed with an error, as shown in Figure 36 and Figure 37, since noise sources appear as areas in the acoustic images and with spreads up to 25 m the offset from the derived blade position. This offset can be explained by the wind dependency and the acoustic behaviour presented e.g. by Buck et al. [27] of wind turbine blade emissions.

Figure 39: Beamforming adaptation results from wind park recordings, sorted by the wind turbine azimuth angle (red rectangles); comparing the actual blade tip positions (blue triangles) with the acoustically processed positions of the maximum (cyan circles)

5.3.5 Discussions

The presented approach of tracking blade noise sources was successfully applied to the measured array wind park data. For a range of wind turbine orientations relative to the microphone array, the approach provided position results that could be used for further investigations and could provide input data for future projects.

Limiting the area of allowed positions based on wind turbine orientation data is beneficial in improving the accuracy of results and finding the blades of the dedicated turbine of interest. On the other hand, does this processing step limit the usability of this approach. For the application of that step the wind turbine data must be available, and the noise sources must be locatable within the selected area. For

different source at a wind turbine other frequency ranges and grid parameters in the algorithm are required and could find other sources of interest.

Applying the frequency range of the $f_c = 4$ kHz 1/3 octave band to the beamformer increased the spatial filtering resolution of blade noise. This tailored adaptation on the monitored wind turbine type Nordex N117 3000 Delta [65] was necessary for accurate blade noise positioning. In other wind turbine type analyses, it could be necessary to apply a different frequency range.

The presented approach is based on the acoustic array data in a combination with axillary sensor data. The development of an implement with an optical sensor processing the wind turbine orientation and other parameters from the recorded images would make the monitoring system independent from operational wind turbine data. This could also provide the information with the needed frequency and accuracy which would increase the algorithm performance. In summary, the process described in the introduction to this section has been implemented and tested in the use case of blade position determination for blade signature processing. This is implemented as a monitoring of the sound signals and enables further investigations on the signal changes over time.

5.4 Conclusion

This Chapter followed the data analysis approaches previously in Section 3.3.4 described and developed the needed algorithms and data processing chains. The first approach of using the continuous recording of robust acquisition hardware at a wind turbine showed the potential for future usage. Found results provided over the long recording comparable results to the current standard approach. It is possible to use the innovative approach as an alternative for wind park noise level evaluation and with that reduce the need for human interaction in measurements. The second analysis proves that an adapted source detection can track specific sound sources. Spatial filtering with microphone array data was used in the development of blade position estimation. The position estimation is robust in different environmental

conditions. In future projects, other sources and a longer recording period should be considered, to prove the adaptation in more detail and wind conditions.

Both approaches showed their applications in wind parks, and both contribute innovative approaches of acoustic monitoring possibilities. In the described scenario of the current developments of one shore wind park the approaches could be applied to reduce noise levels in wind park surroundings with the noise monitoring setup of the array. Further, can the same array enable maintenance based on recorded sounds from the different turbines part and their observation over turbine's operation timeframes.

Chapter 6 Conclusions and Future Work

The hardware development was a significant part of the research project. In this work, the microphone array hardware was the prerequisite for the measurement campaign at the wind farm and the subsequent analysis. The development improved existing hardware approaches of acoustic arrays towards a wind park application as well as combined sensor units. State-of-the-art hardware and data protocols were implemented to achieve the acoustic source separation performance levels required. The detailed analysis of existing hardware and the requirements of the application, with the focus on the microphones' acoustical responses, resulted in tailored hardware and firmware components for the wind park application. Available array hardware and software were analysed, and suitable approaches were adapted to the newly developed microphone array. The protective membrane publication described the adaptation process to wind park acoustic needs in detail. Investigation of the membrane design and manufacturing built up a great understanding of the acoustic behaviour not only of the membrane but also the array structure. Simulations in the membrane development on the vibrational and acoustic membrane behaviours resulted in the design and production of a robust but also acoustically transparent membrane that corresponds to the noise emissions of wind turbines. This developed membrane was integrated into the array structure and was also used for effective weather sealing. This development enabled the first transportable microphone array for continuous outdoor operation. Furthermore, the developed microphone array is the first system with integrated signal processing and sensor fusion capabilities inside each microphone unit.

The developed hardware system was deployed in the wind park to conduct the measurement campaign. Choosing a position for the array was a compromise between the distance and orientation to the wind

turbine, together with the availability of power and a network connection to transfer the captured data. Signal processing was performed in different hardware components and the whole signal processing chain validation was successfully implemented as discussed in Chapter 4. The measured acoustic data from 64 MEMS microphones, wind mast and wind lidar sensors, and the wind turbines operational data provided a great basis for the investigation, data correlations, and algorithm development. Gaps in the auxiliary data series due to sensor malfunction in the two wind sensors were compensated by the other sensor as they were beside each other. The recorded visual images were helpful in manual data inspection during the algorithmic tests.

Data analysis results proved the usability of the microphone array in spatial filtering applications in the wind park. The long-term noise monitoring showed the plausible relations between wind turbine noise and wind turbine's power output. Applied and automated spatial filtering with the recorded data proved that continuous recordings can be utilized in wind turbine monitoring.

The work includes a review of literature about wind turbine noise emissions and acoustic monitoring at wind turbines. The requirements deduced from the literature review were used for the development of the system capable of monitoring noise in wind parks was successful. Data-driven development of analysis methods resulted in two described applications of noise monitoring measures. The first one takes the overall noise recorded at one position in the wind park and derives overall statements on emissions. The second monitoring approach applies spatial filtering to the wind turbine acoustic recordings for blade position estimation.

The developed array monitoring hardware achieved the required performance parameters. The acoustic parameters were achieved by microphone units used in the array, by acquiring sound samples with the required 48 kHz with the presented frequency response. The array achieved the required spatial filtering performance of 5 m x 5 m in the acoustic grid resolution at the wind turbine in the frequency range >1.5 kHz. The developed protective membrane provided the needed array robustness for over 9 weeks of wind park application. With reached application time recording duration outperformed the required 4 weeks of wind park application and recorded 76 hours of acoustic data.

Recorded wind park data were analysed for dependency on the wind direction during recording. The fixed position recordings were evaluated in contrast to multi-position recordings. Both approaches can provide sufficient data for noise load measurements of wind turbines, although the fixed position recording is significantly dependent on changing wind conditions in the wind park. The results from the analysis show the dependency of the noise load from the wind turbine orientation to the recording position. Additionally, the recorded data were used to develop a spatial filtering algorithm. The developed algorithm processes the positions of the wind turbine blades in the prevailing wind conditions and was evaluated against the measured wind turbine data. The results show that the blade positions which are dependent on turbine orientation can be successfully processed based on the acoustic data. The results of Section 5.3 show that the acoustic processed positions follow the wind turbine orientation measured by the turbine. The measured positions can be explained by the occurring effect of wind influences on the sound propagation and a resulting sound wave drift of waves travelling from the wind turbine to the array.

The achieved scientific results were summarised into the main achievements and contributions to science can be summarised as follows:

- An in-depth understanding of a protective membrane for MEMS microphones regarding a consistent, validated empirical model, design guidelines and manufacturing
- The project developed a robust microphone array for wind turbine emission monitoring in terms of frequency response, spatial filtering resolution, and mechanical structure with following subsystems:
 - A digital microphone unit with a processing unit
 - An array mechanical structure optimized for wind park application
- A first acoustic array dataset with 76 hours recording time from a wind park accompanying environmental and turbine operation data has been produced
- An acoustic wind turbine monitoring procedure for data measured with a microphone array at a fixed position in a wind park over an extended period has been developed

- An automated spatial filtering algorithm for wind turbine blade position estimation for blade signature monitoring has been developed and proposed

In Chapter 1 the project aims are described. The general aim was to develop and apply an array monitoring system for continuous acoustic monitoring in wind parks. To achieve that the aim of the requirements for the application of noise monitoring at wind turbines were analysed and identified. The developed array was applied and generated a dataset of spatially recorded acoustic wind turbine emission data. The results presented in Chapter 5 showed that the aim of noise monitoring with an array and the spatial filtering implementation were successfully implemented. Further, the general project objective and its sub-objectives as described in Chapter 3 were achieved. The aims of the hardware development in Section 3.2.1 were fulfilled with the developed array hardware and the successful application of the array in the wind park. The results are presented in Section 4.4 and Section 4.7. The achievement of the required acoustic performance and its application for spatial filtering was proven in Section 4.6 as well as in Figure 36 and Figure 37 with its identification of noise sources at an operating wind turbine. The month-long array operation at one wind turbine meets the expected robustness and performance of acoustic recordings in more than 4 weeks of wind park operation as required in 3.2.2. The recorded acoustic data and the external environmental sensor data were used to develop solutions fulfil the aims in Section 3.2.3 of data analysis. Here two Sections 5.2 and 5.3 show the development of an approach to monitor noise emissions and automate the acoustic source tracking of wind turbine blades. These algorithms prove that the array data could be analysed in the two applications and the results of both Sections prove the array, as well as wind park application, is suitable for acoustic investigations at wind turbines. The data analysis in Section 5.2 proceed results that successfully show the application of noise level monitoring in the wind park with one array system without changing its recording positions. Further, the analysis in Section 5.3 applied automatic sound source localization to the recorded array data. Here, they showed that the spatial filtering algorithm is capable of adapting to the source position in different wind conditions and turbine orientations and with that, fulfils the required accuracy by applying the same spatial filtering algorithm described in Section 4.6.2 to the acoustic array data.

6.1 Future Work

For future work, with the developed microphone array, the signal processing with an adapted frequency range could be directly filtered inside the microphone unit. In this scenario, the raw signals are processed on the site and only wind turbine relevant information is transmitted from the wind park. Potential unwanted audio recordings from sources other than wind turbine sounds are not transmitted. Different array shapes and dimensions could be used for different distances and noise spectra. Additional environmental sensors directly connected to the recording hardware would improve the system autonomy and could improve the sampling rates.

Future work in audio data analysis could apply the developed system and the recorded wind park dataset to a machine learning approach. This approach could provide analyses of turbine maintenance parameters and noise emission changes. Results of this approach would raise operational knowledge on wind turbines in different environmental conditions.

The wind park application was the first attempt to apply a compact transportable outdoor microphone array in a wind turbine range over multiple weeks. The developed hardware could provide a solution for every location where noise is emitted by industrial plants, machinery, or within a city and an investigation on noise sources and their location would help to develop countermeasures. Other application sites could include airports, harbours, traffic sites or construction sites.

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Appendix A: Multi-Sensor-Microphone block diagram

Appendix B: Adaptive spatial filtering analysis

script

```
# -*- coding: utf-8 -*-
"""
Created on Wed Feb  3 15:20:50 2021

@author: Tobias Wenzel

"""
# %% definitions
import os
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import pyuff
from glob import glob
import os.path
import librosa
import librosa.display
import ntpath
from joblib import Parallel, delayed
import multiprocessing
from scipy import signal
from scipy.fft import fft, fftfreq
from scipy.io.wavfile import write
import pandas as pd
import math
import csv
from datetime import timedelta
import datetime
import os.path
from acoustics import acoustics
from pylab import log10
import matplotlib.ticker as plticker
import acoular
import matplotlib
import ntpath
from scipy import signal

import numba
from numba import jit
```

```
from xml.dom import minidom
from windpark_processing_functions import spatialworker, timeworker, worker

from acoular.h5files import H5CacheFileBase, _get_h5file_class
num_cores = multiprocessing.cpu_count()

root = "Z:/01_AudioMeasurements/FieldArray_64"

image_path =
'Z:/01_AudioMeasurements/FieldArray_64/Spectrographs/20200522_windpark/'
AcImage_path = 'Z:/06_Programming/Python/trainingdata/images/'
WAV_path = 'Z:/01_AudioMeasurements/FieldArray_64/WAVexport/'
export_path = 'Z:/01_AudioMeasurements/FieldArray_64/audioexport/'

pattern = "*.uff"
numchannels = 64
parallel_processing = 0
imageoutput = 0
audio_root = "Z:/01_AudioMeasurements/FieldArray_64/20191211_windpark"
audio_pattern = "*.uff"
wind_root = "Z:/02_AuxiliaryMeasurements/windspeed/"
wind_pattern = "*.sta"

wea_path= 'Z:/02_AuxiliaryMeasurements/windspeed/WEA1_data.csv' #contains wind
turbine data
windmast_path= 'Z:/02_AuxiliaryMeasurements/windspeed/windmast_data.csv' #
windmast data 11.05.2020 to05.07.2020

wea_data = pd.read_feather(wind_root +'processed/wea_data_savefile.feather')
wea_data = wea_data.set_index(['Date_time'])

audio_time_table =
pd.read_excel('Z:/01_AudioMeasurements/audio_files_table.xls')

#spatial filtering definitions
miccalibfile = '20210502_fieldarraycalib.xml'
micgeofile = 'array_spiral_field_64_2.xml'
h5_root = "Z:/01_AudioMeasurements/h5_files/"
h5_pattern = '*.h5'

p0 = 0.00002 # 1 Pa SPL reference
cm = 1/2.54 # centimeters in inches
cfreq = [4000]

def spatial_filter(file_idx,file_datetime,index):
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env = acoular.Environment(c = 343) # set up the Environment for the sound
field
blade_length = 116.8/2 # given by the NORDEX N117/3000

rounded_datetime =
spatialworker.roundTime(file_datetime,timedelta(minutes=10))
strinput      = rounded_datetime.strftime("%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S")

mg           = acoular.MicGeom( from_file=micgeofile )
ts           = acoular.MaskedTimeSamples( name = file_idx )
ts.calib     = acoular.Calib(from_file=miccalibfile)
ps           = acoular.PowerSpectra( time_data=ts,
block_size=4096,overlap='50%',\
                                window='Hamming')

# adaption to the WT orientation
# the rotational point is 18,5 m above the center
y_offcenter = 18.5
bladering   = wea_data.loc[strinput].out_bladering_pos
aziAngle    = wea_data.loc[strinput].AzimuthAngle

allowed_pos_window = 25
if bladering<0:
    x_min_temp=np.round ( bladering +allowed_pos_window)#adapt the search
window to the blade pos.
    x_max_temp=np.round ( bladering*(1/2)) #adapt the search window to the
blade pos.
    rg = acoular.RectGrid( x_min=x_min_temp, x_max=x_max_temp,
y_min=(y_offcenter-blade_length), \
                            y_max=0, z=145, increment=1)
elif bladering>=0:

    x_min_temp=np.round ( bladering*(1/2))
    x_max_temp=np.round ( bladering+allowed_pos_window)
    rg = acoular.RectGrid( x_min=x_min_temp, x_max=x_max_temp,
y_min=(y_offcenter-blade_length), \
                            y_max=0, z=145, increment=1)

st = acoular.SteeringVector(grid=rg, mics=mg,env=env)
bb = acoular.BeamformerBase( freq_data=ps, steer=st )
for procssing_freq in cfreq: # single procesing frequency range for the
blade position

    pm = bb.synthetic( procssing_freq, 3 ) #procesing the beamformer
results in freq. domain

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pos_of_max = np.where(pm==pm.max())

x = pos_of_max[0]
y = pos_of_max[1]
if np.size(y)==1 and np.size(x)==1:

    store_x = np.round(x[0]+x_min_temp)
    store_y = np.round(y[0]+(y_offcenter-blade_length))

    if x_max_temp < store_x or store_x < x_min_temp:
        print('outof space')

    grid_pos_points[index][0] = store_x
    print('pos:'+ str(bladering)+ ' --> x:
'+str(grid_pos_points[index][0]))

    grid_pos_points[index][1] = store_y
    grid_pos_points[index][2] = np.round(bladering)

    file_datetime_store.append(file_datetime)
    gridx_store.append(store_x)
    gridy_store.append(store_y)
    gridbaldepos_store.append(np.round(bladering))
    file_store.append(file_idx)

else:
    grid_pos_points[index][0]=np.nan
    grid_pos_points[index][1]=np.nan
    grid_pos_points[index][2]=np.nan

if imageoutput==1:
    mx = acoular.L_p(pm.max())
    figAcMap = plt.figure(6,(10*cm,10*cm))
    # plt.ioff()
    plt.imshow(acoular.L_p(pm.T), origin='lower', vmin=mx-3,
        interpolation='nearest', extent=rg.extend(), cmap='inferno')
    plt.plot([x[0]+x_min_temp],[y[0]+(y_offcenter-blade_length)], 'o')
    plt.colorbar()
    plt.title(str(index)+'_bld'+str(np.round(bladering))+'_azi:'+str(aziAn
gle)+'°_@'+str(procssing_freq)+'hz')

def processInput(index):

    print(index)
    file_idx = filenames['files'].iloc[index]

```

```
# curr_uff_file = pyuff.UFF(file_idx)

filename = ntpath.basename(file_idx)[-3]
print('working with:\n      ' + filename)

try:
    file_rec_time =
audio_time_table.loc[audio_time_table['uff_filename'].str.contains(filename)].
iloc[0].time
    file_rec_date =
audio_time_table.loc[audio_time_table['uff_filename'].str.contains(filename)].
iloc[0].date
    file_rec_date = datetime.datetime.strptime(str(file_rec_date),
'%Y%m%d')

    if isinstance(file_rec_date, datetime.date) and
isinstance(file_rec_time, datetime.time):
        file_datetime =
datetime.datetime.combine(file_rec_date,file_rec_time)
        curr_h5file =file_idx
        spatial_filter(curr_h5file,file_datetime,index)
    else:
        print('no time format')
except:
    print('File ' + filename + ' error ')

### processing start

def controll_process(nsamples):
    if parallel_processing==0:
        for file_idx in filenames.index[np.r[][]]:
            processInput(file_idx)

    elif parallel_processing ==1:
        results = Parallel(n_jobs=num_cores)(delayed(processInput)(file_idx) for
file_idx in uff_files)

if ('uff_files' in globals()):
    print('filelist already there')
else:

    with open('uff_files_file.csv', newline='') as f:
        reader = csv.reader(f)
        uff_files = list(reader)
```

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h5_files = worker.file_finder(h5_root, h5_pattern)
h5_df=pd.DataFrame(h5_files,columns=['files'])
print('done reading')

filenames = h5_df
grid_pos_points = np.zeros((len(uff_files),3))
file_datetime_store = []
gridx_store = []
gridy_store = []
gridbaldepos_store = []
file_store = []

controll_process(1)      # start processing routine
df_grid_pos = pd.DataFrame(data=grid_pos_points)
#combine data and export to csv
df_acoustical_information3 = pd.concat([filenames, df_grid_pos], axis=1)
store_name =
'acoustical_lables_grid_adapt_newset'+str(cfreq[0])+'Hz_wider_3.csv'
df_file_datatime = pd.DataFrame({'file_datetime'      :file_datetime_store,
                                'filenames':file_store,
                                'x_pos':gridx_store,
                                'y_pos':gridy_store,
                                'bladetipos':gridbaldepos_store })

df_file_datatime.to_csv('df_'+store_name, index =False)
df_acoustical_information3.to_csv(store_name,
header=["files", "x_pos", "y_pos", "bladetipos"], index=False)#

```

Supportive functions from windpark_processing_functions.py:

```

# -*- coding: utf-8 -*-
"""
windpark_processing_functions.py
Created on Wed May  5 14:45:11 2021

@author: tobias
"""
import os
import numpy as np
# import tables
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import pyuff
from glob import glob
import os.path
import librosa

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import librosa.display
import ntpath
from joblib import Parallel, delayed
import multiprocessing
from scipy import signal
from scipy.io.wavfile import write
import pandas as pd
import math
import csv
from datetime import datetime, timedelta
import os.path
from acoustics import acoustics
from pylab import log10
import matplotlib.ticker as plticker
import acoular
from arlpy import bf

from numpy import pi, convolve
from scipy.signal.filter_design import bilinear
from scipy.signal import lfilter

import numba
from numba import jit
from xml.dom import minidom

class worker:

    def file_finder(rootdir, extension):
        files = []
        if np.size(rootdir)==1:

            print('searching in ' + rootdir)
            print('searching for: ' + extension)
            for dir,_,_ in os.walk(rootdir):
                files.extend(glob(os.path.join(dir,extension)))

        else:
            for curr_rootdir in rootdir:

                print('searching in ' + curr_rootdir + '\n searching for: ' +
extension)
                #
                for dir,_,_ in os.walk(curr_rootdir):
                    files.extend(glob(os.path.join(dir,extension)))

            return files
```

```
def spl2dB(x):
    p0 = 0.00002
    y = 20*np.log10(np.sqrt(np.mean(np.absolute(x/p0)**2)))
    # y = 20*np.Log10(x/p0)
    return y

def spl2dB_vec(x):
    p0 = 0.00002
    # y = 20*np.Log10(np.sqrt(np.mean(np.absolute(x/p0)**2)))
    y = 20*np.log10(np.abs(x)/p0)
    return y

def A_weighting(Fs):
    # Definition of analog A-weighting filter according to IEC/CD 1672.
    f1 = 20.598997
    f2 = 107.65265
    f3 = 737.86223
    f4 = 12194.217
    A1000 = 1.9997

    NUMs = [(2 * pi * f4)**2 * (10**(A1000/20)), 0, 0, 0, 0]
    DENs = convolve([1, +4 * pi * f4, (2 * pi * f4)**2],
                   [1, +4 * pi * f1, (2 * pi * f1)**2], mode='full')
    DENs = convolve(convolve(DENs, [1, 2 * pi * f3], mode='full'),
                   [1, 2 * pi * f2], mode='full')

    # Use the bilinear transformation to get the digital filter.
    # (Octave, MATLAB, and PyLab disagree about Fs vs 1/Fs)
    return bilinear(NUMs, DENs, Fs)

class timeworker:

    def gen_db SPL_value(file_idx, sum_value):

        Fs = 48000
        numchannels = 64
        miccalibfile = '20210502_fieldarraycalib.xml'
        Y_sum=0
        Y_sum_weighted = 0

        curr_uff_file = pyuff.UFF(file_idx)
        xml_in = minidom.parse(miccalibfile)
        items = xml_in.getElementsByTagName('pos')

        temp_factor =items[0].attributes['factor'].value
        temp = curr_uff_file.read_sets(0)['data']*float(temp_factor)
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y = worker.spl2dB(temp)
B, A, = worker.A_weighting(Fs)
temp_weigthed = lfilter(B, A, temp, axis = 0)
y_weighted = worker.spl2dB(temp_weigthed)

if sum_value ==1:

    for o in range(0,numchannels-1):
        temp_factor =items[o].attributes['factor'].value
        temp = curr_uff_file.read_sets(o)['data']*float(temp_factor)
        temp_weigthed = lfilter(B, A, temp, axis = 0)
        y_weighted = worker.spl2dB(temp_weigthed)

    if o==0:
        Y_sum = worker.spl2dB(temp)
        Y_sum_weighted = y_weighted
    else:
        Y_sum = worker.spl2dB(Y_sum+ temp )
        Y_sum_weighted = Y_sum_weighted+ y_weighted

    Y_sum = Y_sum/numchannels
    Y_sum_weighted = Y_sum_weighted/numchannels

else:
    y_sum = 0
    Y_sum_weighted = 0

return y, y_weighted, Y_sum,Y_sum_weighted

def gen_spectrograph(file_idx,plot_singlechannel_spectrum, store_path):
    Fs = 48000
    data_len = Fs*32
    miccalibfile = '20210502_fieldarraycalib.xml'
    numchannels = 64
    p0 = 0.00002

    cm = 1/2.54
    N, H = 4096, 1024
    curr_uff_file = pyuff.UFF(file_idx)

    xml_in = minidom.parse(miccalibfile)
    items = xml_in.getElementsByTagName('pos')

    Y_sum = np.zeros(data_len)
    x = np.zeros([numchannels,data_len],dtype = float)
    for o in range(0,numchannels-1):
        try:
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temp_factor =items[o].attributes['factor'].value
temp = curr_uff_file.read_sets(o)['data']*float(temp_factor)

if plot_singlechannel_spectrum == 1:
    fig, ax = plt.subplots( figsize=( 8, 5 ), sharex=True )

    N = len(temp)
    yf = np.abs(fft(temp))
    xf = fftfreq(N, 1/48000)[:N//2]
    ax.plot(xf, worker.spl2dB_vec( yf[0:N//2]/N))
    ax.set_ylabel( "amp in dbSPL" )
    ax.set_xlabel( "f in Hz" )
    ax.set_title( "spectrum single channel" )
    ax.set_xlim([0 ,10000])
    ax.grid()
    img_name = store_path + os.path.split(file_idx)[1][0:-
20]+'channel0spectrum.png'
    plt.savefig(img_name, dpi=300)
    fig.clear()
    print('channel spectrum saved')

    plot_singlechannel_spectrum = 0
except:
    print('Channel ' + str(o) + ' read error ')
    print('In file: '+os.path.split(file_idx)[1][0:-21])
    continue

freqs, times, Sx_temp = signal.spectrogram(temp, fs=Fs,
window='hamming',
                                             nperseg=N, noverlap=round(N*0.63),
                                             detrend='constant',
scaling='spectrum', mode='psd' )
    x[0,] = temp;
    if o==0:
        Sx=Sx_temp
        Y_sum = np.abs(fft(temp))
    else:
        Sx=Sx+Sx_temp
        Y_sum = Y_sum+ np.abs(fft(temp))

print('Spectrogram ' + ' read don ')

fig, ax = plt.subplots( figsize=( 8, 5 ), sharex=True )

N = data_len
xf = fftfreq(N, 1/48000)[:N//2]
ax.plot(xf, worker.spl2dB_vec( Y_sum[0:N//2]/N))
ax.set_ylabel( "amp in dbSPL" )

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    ax.set_xlabel( "f in Hz" )
    ax.set_title( "spectrum cummulated channels" )
    ax.set_xlim([0 ,10000])
    ax.grid()
    img_name = store_path + os.path.split(file_idx)[1][0:-
20]+'cumallchannel_spectrum.png'
    plt.savefig(img_name, dpi=300)
    fig.clear()
    print('cum channel spectrum saved')

    frequencies = len(freqs)
    upper_freq =int(round(frequencies/2))
    upper_freq =int(round(frequencies/3))
    lower_freq  =600
    Sx2 = np.resize(Sx, (upper_freq,len(times)))

    #get aux data

    fig= plt.figure(figsize=((13*cm), (6*cm)))
    ax = fig.subplots(1)
    plt.pcolormesh(times,freqs[0: upper_freq]/ 1000,
worker.spl2dB_vec(Sx2), cmap='jet', shading='auto')
    plt.ylabel('Frequency (kHz)')
    plt.title(os.path.split(file_idx)[1][0:-20])
    plt.colorbar(format='%+2.0f dB')
    plt.tight_layout()
    img_name = store_path + os.path.split(file_idx)[1][0:-21]+'.png'
    plt.savefig(img_name, dpi=300)
    print('printed data:\n ' + img_name)
    plt.close()
    fig.clear()

class spatialworker:

    def roundTime(dt, dateDelta):
        """Round a datetime object to a multiple of a timedelta
        dt : datetime.datetime object, default now.
        dateDelta : timedelta object, we round to a multiple of this, default
1 minute.
        Author: Thierry Husson 2012 - Use it as you want but don't blame me.
        Stijn Nevens 2014 - Changed to use only datetime objects as
variables
        """
        roundTo = dateDelta.total_seconds()

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if dt == None : dt = datetime.datetime.now()
seconds = (dt - dt.min).seconds
# // is a floor division, not a comment on following line:
rounding = (seconds+roundTo/2) // roundTo * roundTo
return dt + timedelta(0,rounding-seconds,-dt.microsecond)

def workonacousticmap(file_idx,pm,mg,ts, store_path):

    cm = 1/2.54 # centimeters in inches

    print('in acouatic map')
    Fs = 48000
    data_len = Fs*32

    N, H = 4096, 1024
    #find the maximum value in the acoustic map
    #process the time signal of that position with acoular
    pos_of_max = np.where(pm==pm.max())

    x = pos_of_max[0]
    y = -pos_of_max[1]

    rg_max = acoular.RectGrid( x_min=x, x_max=x, y_min=y, \
                               y_max=y, z=145, increment=1)

    st_max = acoular.SteeringVector(grid=rg_max, mics=mg)

    btsq = acoular.BeamformerTimeSq(source=ts, steer=st_max)
    btsq.r_diag = False
    bt = acoular.BeamformerTime(source=ts, steer=st_max)

    for r in bt.result(data_len): #one single block
        result_samples = r
        wav_name= store_path + file_idx.split('\\')[-1][:-20] +
"timebase.wav"
        write(wav_name, 48000, result_samples.astype(np.float32))
        print('printed data:\n ' + wav_name)

        freqs, times, Sx_temp =
signal.spectrogram(result_samples.transpose(), fs=Fs, window='hamming',
                    nperseg=N, noverlap=round(N*0.63),
                    detrend='constant',
scaling='spectrum', mode='psd' )

        frequencies = len(freqs)
        upper_freq =int(round(frequencies/3))

        Sx2 = np.resize(Sx_temp, (upper_freq,len(times)))

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```

fig= plt.figure(figsize=((13*cm), (6*cm)))
ax = fig.subplots(1)

plt.pcolormesh(times,freqs[20: upper_freq]/ 1000,
worker.spl2dB_vec(Sx2[20:683]), cmap='jet',shading='auto')
plt.xlabel('Time (seconds)')
plt.ylabel('Frequency (kHz)')
plt.title(os.path.split(file_idx)[1][0:-20] + 'timebase')
plt.colorbar(format='%+2.0f dB')
plt.tight_layout()
img_name = store_path + os.path.split(file_idx)[1][0:-
20]+'beamformed_timebase_signal.png'
plt.savefig(img_name, dpi=300)
print('printed data:\n ' + img_name)
plt.close()
fig.clear()

for r in btsq.result(data_len): #one single block

    result_samplessq = r
    write(store_path + file_idx.split('\\')[-1][:-20] + "timeSq.wav",
48000, result_samplessq.astype(np.float32))

    freqs, times, Sx_temp =
signal.spectrogram(result_samplessq.transpose(), fs=Fs, window='hamming',
                    nperseg=N, noverlap=round(N*0.63),
                    detrend='constant',
scaling='spectrum', mode='psd' )

    frequencies = len(freqs)
    upper_freq =int(round(frequencies/3))
    Sx2 = np.resize(Sx_temp, (upper_freq,len(times)))
    fig= plt.figure(figsize=((13*cm), (6*cm)))
    ax = fig.subplots(1)

    # plt.pcolormesh(times,freqs[20: upper_freq]/ 1000, 10 *
np.Log10(Sx2[20:683]), cmap='jet')
    plt.pcolormesh(times,freqs[20: upper_freq]/ 1000,
worker.spl2dB_vec(Sx2[20:683]), cmap='jet',shading='auto')
    plt.xlabel('Time (seconds)')
    plt.ylabel('Frequency (kHz)')
    plt.title(os.path.split(file_idx)[1][0:-20] + 'timeSQ')
    plt.colorbar(format='%+2.0f dB')
    plt.tight_layout()
    img_name = store_path + os.path.split(file_idx)[1][0:-
20]+'beamformed_timesq_signal.png'
    plt.savefig(img_name, dpi=300)

```

```

        print('printed data:\n ' + img_name)
        plt.close()
        fig.clear()

    # result evaluation
    fig, ax = plt.subplots( 2, figsize=( 15, 9 ), sharex=True )

    ax[ 0 ].plot( np.abs(worker.spl2dB_vec(result_samples)), color="b", )
    ax[ 0 ].set_ylabel( "ampl in dB" )
    ax[ 0 ].set_title( "delay and sum beamformer SPL: " +
str(worker.spl2dB(result_samples))+ "dB" )
    ax[ 0 ].grid()

    ax[ 1 ].plot( worker.spl2dB_vec(result_sampllessq), color="k", )
    ax[ 1 ].set_ylabel( "time sq amp in dB" )
    ax[ 1 ].set_xlabel( "samples" )
    ax[ 1 ].set_title( "time SQ beamformer SPL: " +
str(worker.spl2dB(result_sampllessq))+ "dB" )
    ax[ 1 ].grid()

    img_name = store_path + os.path.split(file_idx)[1][0:-
20]+'time_signalcompare.png'
    plt.savefig(img_name, dpi=300)
    fig.clear()

    # calc and display spectrum
    fig, ax = plt.subplots( 2, figsize=( 15, 9 ), sharex=True )

    N = len(result_samples)
    yf = np.abs(fft(result_samples))
    xf = fftfreq(N, 1/48000)[:N//2]
    ax[ 0 ].plot(xf, worker.spl2dB_vec( yf[0:N//2]/N))
    ax[ 0 ].set_ylabel( "base amp" )
    ax[ 0 ].set_title( "spectrum delay and sum beamformer" )
    ax[ 0 ].set_xlim([0 ,10000])
    ax[ 0 ].set_ylim([np.max(worker.spl2dB_vec( yf[0:N//2]/N))-20
,np.max(worker.spl2dB_vec( yf[0:N//2]/N))+5])
    ax[ 0 ].grid()

    N = len(result_sampllessq)
    yf = np.abs(fft(result_sampllessq))
    xf = fftfreq(N, 1/48000)[:N//2]
    ax[ 1 ].plot(xf, worker.spl2dB_vec( yf[0:N//2]/N))
    ax[ 1 ].set_ylabel( "time sq amp" )
    ax[ 1 ].set_title( "spectrum time SQ beamformer" )
    ax[ 1 ].set_xlim([0 ,10000])

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```
ax[ 1 ].set_ylim([np.max(worker.sp12dB_vec( yf[0:N//2]/N))-40
,np.max(worker.sp12dB_vec( yf[0:N//2]/N))+5])
ax[ 1 ].set_xlabel('Frequency in Hz')
ax[ 1 ].grid()

img_name = store_path + os.path.split(file_idx)[1][0:-
20]+'spectrum_signalcompare.png'
plt.savefig(img_name, dpi=300)
fig.clear()
```